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Cost-benefit analysis and socio-economic impact assessment of E-RIHS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

**Prepared by CSIL, Centre for Industrial Studies
This version: December, 2019**

Executive Summary

Background

The European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) is a distributed research infrastructure designed to support research on heritage interpretation, preservation, documentation and management. Being currently in its preparatory phase, it is expected to become a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)¹ in 2023, and after a ramp-up phase of three years (2023-2025), it will operate at full regime (steady-state phase) in 2026. Through standardised protocols and coordinating activities at international level, E-RIHS ERIC will facilitate access to a wide range of physical scientific instruments and digital information for research in heritage science.

E-RIHS builds on a number of EU funded projects benefitting the emerging community of Heritage Science (HS) in Europe. On one side, it is expected to create and shape an identity for the currently fragmented and multidisciplinary scientific community. On the other side, it is expected to facilitate and improve the availability of high-quality services to the community.

In particular E-RIHS will provide access to infrastructures, methodologies, data and tools, training in the use of these tools, public engagement, access to repositories for standardized data storage, analysis and interpretation through four integrated platforms. Four are the key platforms for service delivery:

- ARCHLAB (archives) gives access to specialised knowledge and organized scientific information in datasets largely unpublished from archives of European museums, galleries and research institutions;
- FIXLAB (fixed facilities) gives access to large-scale and medium-scale facilities (particle accelerators and synchrotrons, neutron sources; non-transportable analytical instruments) offering expertise to users for sophisticated scientific investigations on samples or whole objects, e.g. materials, alteration and degradation phenomena or authenticity;
- MOLAB (mobile facilities) offers access to mobile instrumentation for complex multi-technique, and non-invasive measurements on valuable or immovable objects, archaeological sites and historical monuments.
- DIGILAB (virtual facilities) gives access to scientific data concerning tangible heritage, making them FAIR (Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reusable). It includes searchable registries of multidimensional images, analytical data and documentation from large academic as well as research and heritage institutions.

While ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB are designed to offer physical access to already existing instrumentation and tools in a coordinated and streamlined way; the DIGILAB platform will be entirely new and its main goal is to provide FAIR data. In addition, E-RIHS will provide specialised training courses, organise conferences and events and provide information and data to policy makers and citizens through its website.

¹ The European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) is a specific legal form that facilitates the establishment and operation of Research Infrastructures with European interest.

E-RIHS ERIC is a distributed research infrastructure. A Central Hub, based in Florence, operates transnationally as the unique access point to E-RIHS' services. It also provides some specific services such as training courses, conferences and events. In addition, a network of distributed National Hubs, representing the E-RIHS ERIC Member States, the portfolio of services coordinate the national (and regional) providers, which are the entities that ultimately deliver the main access services to users. E-RIHS is expected to give heritage science community a common identity and advance research in heritage science.

This report presents results of the ex-ante impact assessment (IA) of E-RIHS ERIC by discussing the expected direct and indirect impacts in three different scenarios of development (pessimistic, baseline and optimistic). It also discusses the conditions and mechanisms for impact materialisation. This report is meant to provide a decision-making support tool for E-RIHS managers, funding agencies and all the stakeholders involved in its set-up and implementation.

An accompanying technical report includes three annexes: (i) the cost-benefit analysis; (ii) examples and case studies supporting the discussion on wider impacts, and (iii) the descriptive statistics of the answers collected through the surveys.

Methodology

The methodology combines a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) aiming at quantifying direct impacts through the estimation of a willingness to pay of potential users and a qualitative discussion of wider long-term impacts and their pathways. This mixed methods approach has been chosen to better describe the large variety of and multi-faceted potential impacts expected by E-RIHS ERIC. It is solidly grounded on the state-of-the-art theoretical and practical underpinnings of socio-economic impact assessment of RIS² while being tailored to the specificities of heritage science.

This is an ex-ante impact assessment making use of forecasts. Since at the time of writing some of the features regarding E-RIHS ERIC future reach, scope and intensity of use are still under discussion and not fully set, the analysis builds on assumptions on different scenarios on the most likely developments. To cope with the inherent uncertainty of the forecasting exercise and assumptions, quantitative estimates of impacts are provided in probabilistic terms and the assessment is complemented by a risk analysis with Montecarlo simulation.

Sources of evidence include:

- Desk research and literature review (academic and grey works) on the socioeconomic impact of (distributed and e-) research infrastructures;
- Primary data collected through three ad-hoc on-line surveys addressed to the (i) E-RIHS target users; (ii) service providers and (iii) national coordinators. The surveys were open between December 2018 and March 2019 and collected a total of 192 valid questionnaires;
- 20 face-to-face interviews, resulting in more than 30 hours of discussions with E-RIHS ERIC stakeholders and experts;

² See for instance EC (2019), Deliverable 4.1 Concept note of modular impact assessment framework, RIPATHS (Research Infrastructures Impact Assessment Pathways) project. Available from https://ri-paths.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/D4.1_Concept-note-of-modular-IA-framework.pdf

See also Florio (2019); Giffoni and Vignetti (2019, EC (2014)); Giffoni et al (2018); Florio and Sirtori (2016); EMBL-EBI (2016), EC (2014).

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- Existing secondary data were used to triangulate information and fill gaps in primary data and evidence collected via interviews.

Key findings

The provision of services for advancing heritage science is expected to produce different impacts. Some of them are direct as they affect direct users, materialise in a relatively short-term and can be directly attributed to E-RIHS ERIC activities. They have been quantified and expressed in monetary terms.

As expected for any research infrastructure, **the main field of impact is related to the science production. 92% of the total quantified impacts, for a total of EUR 65.9 million in present terms (2017 prices)** in the baseline scenario, relate to an increased efficiency in the science production in the heritage science community, i.e. for E-RIHS target users. Being this community an emerging, multi-disciplinary and currently rather fragmented research community, a unique point of access facilitating and coordinating Trans National Access (TNA) to technologies, data and skills of excellent quality is expected to improve the efficiency (in terms of time saved) and effectiveness (better quality) of the research production in heritage science and related domains. Impacts accounted for under this heading include different, not overlapping but synergic, aspects:

- the facilitation of access to the facilities,
- the production of scientific publications.
- the provision of scientific information, i.e. technical information provided to scientists about the available facilities and how to use them

Facilitation of access is by far the most important impact, accounting for 75% (EUR 49.2 million) of the total science production impact and it materialises in the form of avoided costs (or increase productivity) in scientific production. In particular, access to ARCLAB contributes to EUR 6.4 million (13% of total access impact) to access value, FIXLAB to EUR 6.3 million (12.8%), and MOLAB share is EUR 9.7 million (19.7%). The remaining largest share of EUR 26.9 million (54.5%) is attributable to DIGILAB. In addition, and as a consequence of the access to platforms, E-RIHS also contributes to create new knowledge in terms of scientific publications and citations. It is the second most important general impact generated by E-RIHS and accounts for 24.5% of the science production impact. Still remaining under the science production heading, the item scientific information captures the benefit (mainly time savings) generated by the website of E-RIHS as “one-stop-shop point” where (potential) users can receive information, resolve doubts, and easily access the (virtual) front offices for all services. Such a benefit materialises before and regardless the actual access and use of E-RIHS services and data. It is worth 0.5% (EUR 0.3 million) of that impact.

Beyond purely scientific impact, the HS community will also benefit by **human capital formation, which accounts for 4% of the total quantified impact for a value of EUR 2.7 million** in present terms in the baseline scenario. Training events, including hands-on specialised training either on site or at large-scale facilities, will impact on scientific preparation of young heritage scientists enhancing their capabilities to take stock and exploit the advanced technological offer by the RI for their future careers in the field.

Public engagement and other effects resulting by **dissemination and outreach activities accounts for the remaining 4% of the total quantified impact for a value of EUR 2.9 million** in present terms in the baseline scenario. The E-RIHS ERIC programme of outreach events and services, including information on the web portal and media (including social network) outputs, aimed at informing the general public on advances in

HS (such as permanent or temporary exhibitions, special events, open days, lectures, workshops, conferences, etc.), will impact on the EU citizens as well as public administrations and operators, who will benefit from better non-technical knowledge, awareness and understanding of artistic and cultural assets, including those with potential tourist interest.

Figure 1. Impact of E-RIHS ERIC - baseline scenario (EUR 2017)

Source: Authors

The costs of E-RIHS were calculated according to the guidelines provided by the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)³ and include investment and operating costs. The total investment costs of E-RIHS ERIC cover costs incurred during the preparatory phase⁴ and amount to EUR 20.7 million (at 2017 prices). Differently, the operating costs are all the outlays needed to operate and maintain E-RIHS ERIC during its life-cycle. They encompass both in-kind and cash contribution as well as fixed items, i.e. items that do not (or only marginally) vary when the size of activities changes (e.g. the operating costs of the Central Hub) and variable items. The source of operating costs is the cost-book of E-RIHS ERIC.

If total investment and operating costs of E-RIHS ERIC are confronted with the above impacts (benefits), the analysis points to an **economic net present value (ENPV) equal to EUR 11.3 million, an economic rate of return of 6.02% and a B/C ratio of 1.20** in the baseline scenario. The set up and implementation of E-RIHS ERIC will then yield positive net impacts to the society mainly by enhancing the productivity of heritage scientific community.

The scenario and risk analyses highlight that these positive results hold as long as the assumptions reflected in the analysis are verified. In particular, **two conditions are key for success: the number of users at the steady state and the degree of coordination and integration (added value) of services provided.**

In terms of **number of users**, it is important that the actual number of users accessing ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB will reach about 800 units at the steady state (full regime) in 2026 and stay on this trajectory further in the future. More importantly, it has been estimated that, based on the assumptions, the minimum number of TNA users needed to avoid a negative ENPV is 650. Below this threshold, the ENPV turns to be negative:

³ Guidelines on Cost Estimation of Research Infrastructures. Report by StR-ESFRI – Support to Reinforce the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures. Available from https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/StR-ESFRI2_STUDY_RIs_COST_ESTIMATION.pdf

⁴ This also includes the costs of IPERION CH and IPERION HS, which are part of the investment phase (see below).

costs will exceed benefits and the project will be not worthy for the society (the project will be likely to use more resources more than it will produce).

In addition, the success of the infrastructure relies on the extent to which the integrated and coordinated nature of the services provided to the heritage science community ensure **an added value for users with respect to any counterfactual scenario** (i.e. the provision of the same services in a non-coordinated and non-integrated way, a 'no E-RIHS' scenario). The added value (the impact) increases as long as coordination and integration between platforms improves and the FAIRness principle of data in DIGILAB is pursued.

The activities of E-RIHS ERIC have the potential to achieve wider socioeconomic impacts. They can materialise in the long-term in other markets and sectors, provided that certain internal and external enabling conditions are ensured. For their nature, wider economic impacts are difficult to be quantified. They include the contribution of E-RIHS ERIC to the analysis and preservation of the European cultural heritage, to policies and regulations in the field of heritage science thanks to the science diplomacy activity and impacts on the tourism industry and services. These impacts can be facilitated by E-RIHS ERIC but to fully materialise they will need additional investments, activities and actions from different stakeholders. They relate in particular to:

- **Science diplomacy and impact on cultural policies.** These impacts can include both effects in terms of cultural identity at a national and European level as well as cultural diplomacy and soft power outcomes on bilateral and international relations. Institutional activities including participating in international conferences and events, as well as advocacy activities related to cultural activities and policies may have positive impacts not only on cultural policies but also on broad international diplomatic relationships. This holds true in as much as the global reach of E-RIHS activities is achieved. The inclusion of E-RIHS in the GSO as well as its collaboration with ICCROM are paving the way to that.
- **Impact on access to culture and on cultural tourism.** Tourist/access effects can derive from innovation processes in museums and cultural sites triggered by the knowledge and experience developed in the context of E-RIHS ERIC activities and further exploited downstream. They may take the form of design of new products and services to enrich the cultural offer, construction of new narratives and communication tools targeted to visitors, etc.

Based on this analysis and thinking the socioeconomic impact as process rather than as product of E-RIHS' activities, the following actions can keep the initiative on the right pathways for impacts:

- **A sustainable level of demand aiming at reaching the number of TNA users of physical platforms foreseen in the baseline scenario should be ensured.** The CBA indicates that there is a break-even point at 650 TNA users. Under this level of demand, costs to provide a coordinated and unique access exceed their benefits and the ENPV turns to be negative. Increasing the share of machine- and personnel-time for E-RIHS users, expanding the network of affiliated facilities, and ensuring a good level of coordination among spatially distributed providers can increase the appeal of E-RIHS services. In parallel, information campaigns aiming at reducing the information gap experienced by potential users as regards the type of services and facilities offered, mode of access, and the necessary skills to use instrumentation are likely to increase the users' awareness about the value of services provided. However, a critical aspect is the capacity to ensure the coverage of financial costs to access E-RIHS (e.g. cost of travel and subsistence to access services, cost of transportation and insurance for mobile machine).

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- **Efforts should be concentrated to create high added-value services for users.** The existence of E-RIHS is legitimised as long as it makes easier and cheaper the access to existing facilities, and therefore offering services that add value as compared to the existing access situation. The removal of administrative, managerial, and cultural barriers depends on to what extent E-RIHS will be able to coordinate users when accessing (e.g. providing assistance in developing project proposals, help desk activities, conveying complete and clear information via its web portal), to offer integrating services (e.g. access to multiple platforms and complementary research equipment), and actually providing FAIR data via DIGILAB. It is also advised to continue with training courses (e.g. training camps, summer schools), which represent valuable services from the attendees' viewpoint.
 - **Contributing to the preparation of a policy agenda for heritage science by adopting a prioritisation mechanism for the identification of the community's needs** should be considered among the internal enabling conditions to make E-RIHS a key actor for heritage science policy. Science diplomacy, support to policy design with programming and regulatory tools, and advocacy can be triggered by E-RIHS by facilitating a close dialogue among its partners, organising international conferences, increasing its international visibility, and participating at heritage science events. These activities help build an identity and make E-RIHS' voice heard when interfacing with policy-makers and key institutions in setting the policy agenda at the international level.
 - **The engagement of actors such as SMEs (or their representativeness) and operators in the cultural tourism sector** is an additional enabling condition to trigger downstream impacts. While the main mission of E-RIHS is to promote excellence in research, and therefore downstream impacts are beyond its main scope, **co-creation is likely to create the bridge linking E-RIHS research activities to the economy by means of knowledge transfer to firms and cultural and tourism operators.** Collaboration practises between researchers and firms during a research project or further dissemination and communication activities can produce a mutually valuable outcome: researchers make their results usable beyond the scientific community; firms may increase their innovation capabilities and develop new products and services to be used in the cultural tourism sector.
 - **E-RIHS ERIC management should keep track of the identified Key Performance Indicators for future monitoring and evaluation activities, which should be driven by the logic model developed ad-hoc for E-RIHS.** The idea of the societal impact as a process requires to periodically monitor whether deviations from the ex-ante forecasts, targets or modified enabling conditions occur and in that case assess to what extent they can jeopardise the impact of E-RIHS on the reference group of users. Updates of the current analysis or new evaluation exercises can be considered in the future as strategic tool to ensure that E-RIHS ERIC is on the right pathway and (new) objectives are within reach.

Cost-benefit analysis and socio-economic impact assessment of E-RIHS

**Prepared by CSIL, Centre for Industrial Studies
This version: December, 2019**

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Abbreviations

ADS	Archaeology Data Services
B/C ratio	Benefit/cost ratio
CBA	Cost-benefit analysis
CERIC-ERIC	Research Infrastructure open for basic and applied users in the fields of Materials, Biomaterials and Nanotechnology
CHARISMA	Cultural Heritage Advanced Research Infrastructures: Synergy for a Multidisciplinary Approach to Conservation/Restoration
CNR-INO	Istituto Nazionale di Ottica
CSIL	Centre for Industrial Studies
DARIAH-ERIC	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
E-RIHS PP	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Preparatory Phase
EMBL-EBI	European Bioinformatics Institute
ENPV	Economic Net Present Value
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ERR	Economic Rate of Return
ESDS	Economic and Social Data Service
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
Eu-ARTECH	Access, Research and Technology for the conservation of the European Cultural Heritage
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GSO	Group of Senior Officials of Global Research Infrastructures
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
HS	Heritage Science
IPERION CH	Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Cultural Heritage
ICCROM	International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property
IT	Italy
JPI CH	Joint Programming Initiative Cultural Heritage
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LabS TECH	Laboratories on Science and Technology for the conservation of European Cultural Heritage
PARTHENOS	Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies
RI	Research Infrastructure
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineers and Mathematics.
SSH	Social Science Humanities
SSHOC	Social Science Humanities Open Cloud
TCM	Travel Cost Method
TNA	Transnational access

Executive Summary

Background

The European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) is a distributed research infrastructure designed to support research on heritage interpretation, preservation, documentation and management. Being currently in its preparatory phase, it is expected to become a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)¹ in 2023, and after a ramp-up phase of three years (2023-2025), it will operate at full regime (steady-state phase) in 2026. Through standardised protocols and coordinating activities at international level, E-RIHS ERIC will facilitate access to a wide range of physical scientific instruments and digital information for research in heritage science.

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E-RIHS ERIC is a distributed research infrastructure. A Central Hub, based in Florence, operates transnationally as the unique access point to E-RIHS' services. It also provides some specific services such as training courses, conferences and events. In addition, a network of distributed National Hubs, representing the E-RIHS ERIC Member States, the portfolio of services coordinate the national (and regional) providers, which are the entities that ultimately deliver the main access services to users. E-RIHS is expected to give heritage science community a common identity and advance research in heritage science.

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An accompanying technical report includes four annexes: (i) the cost-benefit analysis; (ii) the descriptive statistics of the answers collected through the surveys, (iii) examples and case studies supporting the discussion on wider impacts, and (iv) a discussion on the potential impact of E-RIHS Central hub on the city of Florence.

Methodology

The methodology combines a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) aiming at quantifying direct impacts through the estimation of a willingness to pay of potential users and a qualitative discussion of wider long-term impacts and their pathways. This mixed methods approach has been chosen to better describe the large variety of and multi-faceted potential impacts expected by E-RIHS ERIC. It is solidly grounded on the state-of-the-art theoretical and practical underpinnings of socio-economic impact assessment of RIs² while being tailored to the specificities of heritage science.

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Key findings

The provision of services for advancing heritage science is expected to produce different impacts. Some of them are direct as they affect direct users, materialise in a relatively short-term and can be directly attributed to E-RIHS ERIC activities. They have been quantified and expressed in monetary terms.

As expected for any research infrastructure, **the main field of impact is related to the science production. 92% of the total quantified impacts, for a total of EUR 65.9 million in present terms (2017 prices) in the baseline scenario, relate to an increased efficiency in the science production in the heritage science community, i.e. for E-RIHS target users.** Being this community an emerging, multi-disciplinary and currently rather fragmented research community, a unique point of access facilitating and coordinating Trans National Access (TNA) to technologies, data and skills of excellent quality is expected to improve the efficiency (in terms of time saved) and effectiveness (better quality) of the research production in heritage science and related domains. Impacts accounted for under this heading include different, not overlapping but synergic, aspects:

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Figure 1. Impact of E-RIHS ERIC - baseline scenario (EUR 2017)

Source: Authors

The costs of E-RIHS were calculated according to the guidelines provided by the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)³ and include investment and operating costs. The total investment costs of E-RIHS ERIC cover costs incurred during the preparatory phase⁴ and amount to EUR 20.7 million (at 2017 prices). Differently, the operating costs are all the outlays needed to operate and maintain E-RIHS ERIC during its life-cycle. They encompass

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⁴ This also includes the costs of IPERION CH and IPERION HS, which are part of the investment phase (see below).

both in-kind and cash contribution as well as fixed items, i.e. items that do not (or only marginally) vary when the size of activities changes (e.g. the operating costs of the Central Hub) and variable items. The source of operating costs is the cost-book of E-RIHS ERIC.

If total investment and operating costs of E-RIHS ERIC are confronted with the above impacts (benefits), the analysis points to an **economic net present value (ENPV) equal to EUR 11.3 million, an economic rate of return of 6.02% and a B/C ratio of 1.20** in the baseline scenario. The set up and implementation of E-RIHS ERIC will then yield positive net impacts to the society mainly by enhancing the productivity of heritage scientific community.

The scenario and risk analyses highlight that these positive results hold as long as the assumptions reflected in the analysis are verified. In particular, **two conditions are key for success: the number of users at the steady state and the degree of coordination and integration (added value) of services provided.**

In terms of **number of users**, it is important that the actual number of users accessing ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB will reach about 800 units at the steady state (full regime) in 2026 and stay on this trajectory further in the future. More importantly, it has been estimated that, based on the assumptions, the minimum number of TNA users needed to avoid a negative ENPV is 650. Below this threshold, the ENPV turns to be negative: costs will exceed benefits and the project will be not worthy for the society (the project will be likely to use more resources more than it will produce).

In addition, the success of the infrastructure relies on the extent to which the integrated and coordinated nature of the services provided to the heritage science community ensure **an added value for users with respect to any counterfactual scenario** (i.e. the provision of the same services in a non-coordinated and non-integrated way, a 'no E-RIHS' scenario). The added value (the impact) increases as long as coordination and integration between platforms improves and the FAIRness principle of data in DIGILAB is pursued.

The activities of E-RIHS ERIC have the potential to achieve wider socioeconomic impacts. They can materialise in the long-term in other markets and sectors, provided that certain internal and external enabling conditions are ensured. For their nature, wider economic impacts are difficult to be quantified. They include the contribution of E-RIHS ERIC to the analysis and preservation of the European cultural heritage, to policies and regulations in the field of heritage science thanks to the science diplomacy activity and impacts on the tourism industry and services. These impacts can be facilitated by E-RIHS ERIC but to fully materialise they will need additional investments, activities and actions from different stakeholders. They relate in particular to:

- **Science diplomacy and impact on cultural policies.** These impacts can include both effects in terms of cultural identity at a national and European level as well as cultural diplomacy and soft power outcomes on bilateral and international relations. Institutional activities including participating in international conferences and events, as well as advocacy activities related to cultural activities and policies may have positive impacts not only on cultural policies but also on broad international diplomatic relationships. This holds true in as much as the global reach of E-RIHS activities is achieved. The inclusion of E-RIHS in the GSO as well as its collaboration with ICCROM are paving the way to that.

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- **Impact on access to culture and on cultural tourism.** Tourist/access effects can derive from innovation processes in museums and cultural sites triggered by the knowledge and experience developed in the context of E-RIHS ERIC activities and further exploited downstream. They may take the form of design of new products and services to enrich the cultural offer, construction of new narratives and communication tools targeted to visitors, etc.

Based on this analysis and thinking the socioeconomic impact as process rather than as product of E-RIHS' activities, the following actions can keep the initiative on the right pathways for impacts:

- **A sustainable level of demand aiming at reaching the number of TNA users of physical platforms foreseen in the baseline scenario should be ensured.** The CBA indicates that there is a break-even point at 650 TNA users. Under this level of demand, costs to provide a coordinated and unique access exceed their benefits and the ENPV turns to be negative. Increasing the share of machine- and personnel-time for E-RIHS users, expanding the network of affiliated facilities, and ensuring a good level of coordination among spatially distributed providers can increase the appeal of E-RIHS services. In parallel, information campaigns aiming at reducing the information gap experienced by potential users as regards the type of services and facilities offered, mode of access, and the necessary skills to use instrumentation are likely to increase the users' awareness about the value of services provided. However, a critical aspect is the capacity to ensure the coverage of financial costs to access E-RIHS (e.g. cost of travel and subsistence to access services, cost of transportation and insurance for mobile machine).
- **Efforts should be concentrated to create high added-value services for users.** The existence of E-RIHS is legitimised as long as it makes easier and cheaper the access to existing facilities, and therefore offering services that add value as compared to the existing access situation. The removal of administrative, managerial, and cultural barriers depends on to what extent E-RIHS will be able to coordinate users when accessing (e.g. providing assistance in developing project proposals, help desk activities, conveying complete and clear information via its web portal), to offer integrating services (e.g. access to multiple platforms and complementary research equipment), and actually providing FAIR data via DIGILAB. It is also advised to continue with training courses (e.g. training camps, summer schools), which represent valuable services from the attendees' viewpoint.
- **Contributing to the preparation of a policy agenda for heritage science by adopting a prioritisation mechanism for the identification of the community's needs** should be considered among the internal enabling conditions to make E-RIHS a key actor for heritage science policy. Science diplomacy, support to policy design with programming and regulatory tools, and advocacy can be triggered by E-RIHS by facilitating a close dialogue among its partners, organising international conferences, increasing its international visibility, and participating at heritage science events. These activities help build an identity and make E-RIHS' voice heard when interfacing with policy-makers and key institutions in setting the policy agenda at the international level.
- **The engagement of actors such as SMEs (or their representativeness) and operators in the cultural tourism sector** is an additional enabling condition to trigger downstream impacts. While the main mission of E-RIHS is to promote excellence in research, and therefore downstream impacts are beyond its main scope, **co-creation is likely to create**

the bridge linking E-RIHS research activities to the economy by means of knowledge transfer to firms and cultural and tourism operators. Collaboration practises between researchers and firms during a research project or further dissemination and communication activities can produce a mutually valuable outcome: researchers make their results usable beyond the scientific community; firms may increase their innovation capabilities and develop new products and services to be used in the cultural tourism sector.

- **E-RIHS ERIC management should keep track of the identified Key Performance Indicators for future monitoring and evaluation activities, which should be driven by the logic model developed ad-hoc for E-RIHS.** The idea of the societal impact as a process requires to periodically monitor whether deviations from the ex-ante forecasts, targets or modified enabling conditions occur and in that case assess to what extent they can jeopardise the impact of E-RIHS on the reference group of users. Updates of the current analysis or new evaluation exercises can be considered in the future as strategic tool to ensure that E-RIHS ERIC is on the right pathway and (new) objectives are within reach.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

By 2023, when the European consortium is expected to be operational, E-RIHS ERIC will manage state-of-art tools, data and services on a large scale, making a rich range of resources and information freely available to the cross-disciplinary users and scientific communities in heritage science. It will contribute to the growth of the European Research Area (ERA) by reducing fragmentation, duplication of efforts, isolation of small research groups that negatively contribute to the competitive advantage of European heritage science research. E-RIHS joins the European Open Science Cloud – hub (EOSC-hub)⁵ project and in 2016 it was included as a landmark in the ESFRI roadmap.⁶

As part of the preparatory phase, E-RIHS required a socio-economic impact assessment of its work, including a CBA.

1.2 Methodology

The methodology adopted in this report is a combination of a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) and a qualitative socio-economic impact assessment. CBA is routinely carried out by national administrations and international organisation to appraise infrastructure projects funded with public resources.⁷ In context of this study, standard economic techniques (including marginal cost of production; travel cost method; avoided cost method) were used to quantify non-market values of E-RIHS ERIC services to direct users (technical details are included in Annex I). Moreover, qualitative methods (case studies and logic pathways) were adopted to describe its impacts on the wider communities such as policy makers in charge of cultural heritage policies, industries operating in the tourism sector, citizens exposed to E-RIHS ERIC outreach, and discuss local effects on the city of Florence.

⁵ <http://www.e-rihs.eu/tag/eosc/> . For details on the EOSC-hub project see <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/about-us>

⁶ ESFRI contributes to the development of a coherent strategy for the development of research infrastructures in Europe, and acts as an incubator by facilitating multilateral initiatives and international negotiations on their use and sustainability. Periodically, ESFRI lays down the Roadmap of research infrastructures of pan-European dimension in all fields of research. The Roadmap identifies new research infrastructure proposals of European interest, or projects to upgrade infrastructures already active, and is an indispensable tool to facilitate decision-making by Member States and the European Commission. The 2021 ESFRI Roadmap is available here: <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-roadmap-2021>

⁷ The CBA is systematically used by DG-REGIO to appraise (major) public investment decisions in order to assess the welfare change that is attributable to it. According to the CBA guideline by DG-REGIO (EC, 2014), the CBA the solidity of the CBA relies on four key ingredients: (i) Microeconomic perspective based on the idea that the welfare change produced by a project comes primarily from the added value its produces from users through the conventional rules of adding consumer, producer, and taxpayers surpluses; (ii) The incremental approach, i.e. comparing the with-the-project scenario with a counterfactual baseline without-the-project scenario; (iii) Long-term perspective, i.e. using a long-term outlook (e.g. from 30 to 50 years) to account for the fact that the benefits to society that are generated by a project may materialise in the very far future; (iv) a risk assessment must be included in the CBA to deal with the uncertainty that always permeates the appraisal of investment projects. The encouraging recent applications of the CBA for the assessment of research infrastructures (e.g. Florio and Sirtori, 2016; Florio 2019) lead to the 2016 ESFRI roadmap to recognise the contribution of CBA in providing robust evidence on the assessment of their socioeconomic impacts (ESFRI, 2016).

Importantly, this is an ex-ante evaluation which makes use of forecasts and assumptions on possible future scenarios on E-RIHS ERIC geographical scope and intensity of use, whose key features are currently still debated. Assumptions rely on a combination of data and activities carried out by the evaluation team including:

- Desk research and literature review (academic and grey works) on the socioeconomic impact of (distributed and e-) research infrastructures;
- Primary data collected through three ad-hoc on-line surveys designed by the team and addressed to the (i) E-RIHS target users; (ii) providers of services such as archives, synchrotrons, particle accelerators and mobile laboratories, and (iii) national coordinators. The surveys were distributed via Survey Monkey© between December 2018 and March 2019 and collected 164 valid questionnaires of users (60% actual and 40% potential), 13 from service providers and 15 national coordinators for a total of 192 valid interviews⁸;
- In parallel with surveys, 20 face-to-face interviews, resulting in more than 30 hours of discussions, were carried out with E-RIHS ERIC stakeholders and experts on the impact of research infrastructures;
- Existing secondary data were used to triangulate information and fill gaps in primary data and evidence collected via interviews.

Table 1. Contents of the three surveys

	E-RIHS target users	Providers	National coordinators
Aim	Identify research needs of (potential) users, their personal goals in relation to the E-RIHS ERIC project and the expected impact of that project on research and other activities.	Identify costs to support E-RIHS ERIC, involvement in the project, research needs, reasons of their willingness to join E-RIHS ERIC and expected impact on their activities	Forecasting the number of potential providers, required additional investments and expected impacts
Target	Two target samples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - users of E-RIHS ERIC predecessors (Eu-ARTECH, CHARISMA, IPERIOCH CH and ARIADNE) and existing e-infrastructures (CLARIN, DARIAH, and ARIADNE) - potential users, i.e. people whose work/study in the heritage science 	Providers of facilities and data	National coordinators

The layout of the remaining part of this report is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the objectives, structure and activities of E-RIHS. Section 3 presents the logic model that has guided the identification and assessment of impacts. Section 4 describes the main assumptions underlying the analysis; while Section 5 presents the costs of E-RIHS ERIC. The direct impacts and their values are reported in Section 6; while Section 7 discusses the wider impacts as well as conditions for materialisations. Section 8 concludes and includes the main messages. Further details on the assumptions, calculation of costs and benefits, evidence supporting the wider impacts are discussed in an accompanying technical report, which includes: (i) the cost-benefit analysis; (ii) examples and case studies supporting the wider impacts, and (iii) the descriptive statistics of the answers collected through the surveys.

⁸ Surveys results can be found in Annex II

1.3 Intended audience

This report is primarily addressed to:

- E-RIHS ERIC managers and members of the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) who, at the time of writing, are designing the consortium structure, costs and policies to support evidence-based decision making.
- Funders of E-RIHS ERIC, including the European Commission, Member States and national providers that contribute via in-kind contributions. The impact assessment raises their awareness on costs and benefits generated by the core research activities of E-RIHS ERIC and, the extent to which their effects spread out beyond the research community to the wider society, including firms, policy makers and citizens.

In addition, the report can inform heritage science community to raise its awareness about having a research infrastructure designed to facilitate access to state-of-the-art research tools and data. Finally, distributed research infrastructures similar to E-RIHS ERIC that delivers digital and/or physical services can benefit from the discussion of a logic model and a way of thinking to understand, identify and track potential impacts on the research community they refer to.

2. Background and description of E-RIHS ERIC

2.1 History

E-RIHS ERIC is the result of a long-lasting experience of integrated activities of advanced and emerging research communities started in 2001 when the LabS TECH consortium was established (2001-2004).⁹ Funded by EU funds for limited periods of time, all the predecessors projects of E-RIHS ERIC had the final long-term aim of creating a long-lasting, self-sustainable, and pan-European distributed large-scale facility in the field of heritage science capable of capitalising preceding efforts and ensuring long-term impacts.

Labs TECH was the first project and consisted of 8 Member States and 11 providers. It aimed at realizing a complementarity among the most international distinguished European laboratories working in the field of scientific and technological applications to the conservation and restoration of cultural heritage through interchange of know-how and joining of resources. The projects that have followed involved an increasing number of Member States and developed a number of services, increasingly contributing to design and test the structure E-RIHS is going to assume. Indeed, the three platforms included in E-RIHS (ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB) have started to be developed since Eu-ARTECH (2004 – 2009),¹⁰ which pursued a permanent interoperability among the participating infrastructures, establishing cooperation and exchange of knowledge with the other infrastructures in the field. Eu-ARTECH was further complemented and developed by major EU-funded integration research and infrastructural projects such as CHARISMA (2009-2014)¹¹ and IPERION CH (2014-2019)¹² in conservation/restoration science. CHARISMA brought together 22 leading European institutions developing research on artwork materials and their deterioration finalised to the conservation of cultural heritage. The project reinforced networking, improved the way infrastructures was working by harmonising methodologies and best practices in analysis and conservation. IPERION CH further expanded the network and it is currently providing some of the services that E-RIHS ERIC will provide in the future. Built on this experience and with the ambition of establishing a permanent leading European RI in heritage science, in 2016 E-RIHS entered into the ESFRI Roadmap to become an ERIC¹³.

⁹ The Laboratories on Science and Technology for the conservation of European Cultural Heritage (LabS TECH) https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/53831_en.html

¹⁰ Eu-ARTECH (Access, Research and Technology for the conservation of the European Cultural Heritage) https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/73812_en.html

¹¹ CHARISMA (Cultural Heritage Advanced Research Infrastructures: Synergy for a Multidisciplinary Approach to Conservation/Restoration) https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/92569_en.html

¹² IPERION CH (Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Cultural Heritage) is an ongoing project. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/198068/factsheet/en>

¹³ The European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) is a specific legal form that facilitates the establishment and operation of Research Infrastructures with European interest.

Figure 2. Predecessors of E-RIHS ERIC¹⁴

Source: authors

2.2 Context: challenges of an emerging scientific domain

First defined in 2006,¹⁵ “the term ‘heritage science’ is becoming increasingly adopted as a means to unify a number of interrelated applied science fields [...] which focus on the study of cultural heritage under one umbrella to create a stronger, more cohesive and readily recognizable field with greater critical mass”.¹⁶ As an emerging transdisciplinary scientific domain with the ambition of providing a holistic approach to cultural and natural heritage preservation, documentation, interpretation and management, it is characterised by a number of challenges.

2.2.1 A multidisciplinary and fragmented scientific community

Heritage science can be seen as a melting pot of scientists from different disciplines, policy makers, and practitioners from both private and public institutions, who need to interact with each other in order to document, interpret, analyse, preserve, and manage cultural heritage.

From a scientific perspective, although the Heritage Science seems still dominated by STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) disciplines,¹⁷ it has been increasingly becoming a multidisciplinary domain. STEM disciplines are today flanked by SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities) subjects as well as hybrid and interdisciplinary disciplines such as archaeometry, conservation science and technical art history (Figure 3). Such a variety of research areas, scientists (and professionals) ensure the presence of different skills and

¹⁴ For details on E-RIHS ERIC predecessors see the CBA annex.

¹⁵ Strlič, M. (2018). Heritage Science: A Future-Oriented Cross-Disciplinary Field, Guest Editorial, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 2018, 57, 2 – 4

¹⁶ (ICCROM, 2015). International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property. <https://www.iccrom.org/>

¹⁷ For instance, most of publications in the journal ‘Heritage Science’ are related to STEM subjects. Our interviews also confirm this evidence (see below).

competencies to examine an extremely wide range of heritage objects, from micro samples of heritage artefacts to paintings, monuments, and ancient texts.

Figure 3. Disciplines in the heritage science domain

Source: authors.

While necessary, the interdisciplinarity is not enough without a consolidated transdisciplinary working practice which is still missing. This makes collaboration challenging due to obstacles in terms of communication and interpersonal relationships in team-working among people with different backgrounds, working methods, languages and practices. Collaboration is further complicated by the differences in intra-institutional procedures (more details below), as shown by the literature on research collaboration in heritage science.¹⁸

From a policy (and management) perspective, the use and access to cultural heritage mask a complex decision problem because of the presence of different objectives to be pursued, the public/private nature of the goods under investigation, the existence of several values (historical, artistic, cultural, economic, etc.), the presence of different actors (public government representatives, curators, architectural historians, developers and owners).¹⁹ This points to the necessity of building a precise identity to this still emerging and fragmented scientific community, while enhancing cohesion and integration.

2.2.2 Restricted availability and access to technological tools and facilities

Heritage Science is an applied scientific domain oriented to produce practical benefits in terms of better understanding, analysing, preserving and managing of the cultural heritage.²⁰ This requires a high level and wide variety of skills, data, advanced instruments and technologies which are sometimes unavailable or not easily accessible by the researchers. Barriers encompass access prohibition to external users (e.g. access limitation to archives in museums or particle accelerators, scanners, etc. owned by research institutions), lack of machine time in case of full capacity exploitation (e.g. beam lines of a synchrotron), financial barriers (e.g. supporting the expenses for transportation, insurance, and usage of highly sophisticated mobile equipment), lack of skills, competences and awareness (e.g. skills for the use of the equipment and even the

¹⁸ Katrakazis et al. (2018), Dillon et al. (2014).

¹⁹ Ferretti et al (2014).

²⁰ ICCROM (2015).

lack of knowledge of existing techniques), but also administrative barriers due, for instance, to the lack of established institutional and legal arrangements for transboundary access. Moreover, the literature has recently claimed for implementation of open data sharing practices (e.g. accessibility, re-use, redistribution, participation)²¹. The necessity of having access to data and facilities, obtaining them in a more efficient way as well as reducing asymmetric information and gaps about existing methods and up-to-date research procedures is clearly identified as an emerging need.²²

2.2.3 Institutional and administrative fragmentation

A recent mapping to the heritage science community,²³ shows that the wide variety of institutions involved in the analysis and the management of cultural heritage differ in terms of location, core activities, dimensions and legal status, implying differences in internal research rules, access procedures and protocols. The administrative fragmentation makes the transnational collaboration and access to facilities cumbersome and discouraging even when an access policy is in place. Moreover, this prevents an effective, efficient and high-quality research because of restricted share of technologies for analysis, content, and knowledge between heritage institutions.²⁴ The difficulty to collaborate across institutional, disciplinary, and geographic borders points to the necessity of designing codes of practice for research specifically developed for the heritage science community. Such as protocols should also include policy guidelines to include heritage science operators from different institutions in research production, crossing the academic border²⁵.

2.3 Governance and funding structure

E-RIHS ERIC has been conceived to address the challenges discussed above and meet the heritage science community's necessities through an ad-hoc governance and funding structure, customised services, and access policy.

E-RIHS ERIC is a distributed RI with a legal structure based on two operational levels.

The first level is represented by the E-RIHS ERIC Central Hub, which is based in Florence. It operates transnationally as the unique access point to services (facilities, competences, skills, training courses, content) provided by E-RIHS ERIC potentially joint to one or more Help Desk(s) that are expected to act as a bridge between user's research question and all the potential providers of one or more platforms to identify and direct users to the adequate facilities, as well as assisting the potential users in elaborating their research proposals. The Central Hub interacts with the distributed National Hubs (via the National Coordinators Committee) to manage in a coordinated and integrated manner the portfolio of services listed in the catalogue (see below). Other activities it is expected to perform are ensuring E-RIHS ERIC services are properly delivered to users and dealing with management and communication matters. The Central Hub interacts with the National Hubs, but it does not liaise with individual access providers and/or facilities at

²¹ Katrakazis et al. (2018)

²² Evidence based on interviews.

²³ ICCROM (2016); Dillon et al. (2014)

²⁴ Evidence from interviews to operators.

²⁵ Katrakazis et al. (2018).

national or regional level. In order to accomplish its duties, the Central Hub hosts a direction office and a head office. Specifically, the Central Hub is in charge of the E-RIHS ERIC implementation strategy and of providing core activities²⁶. These latter are expected to be organised in three units: ²⁷

1. *The Access Unit*, i.e. the users' interface, will manage the calls and services, providing general information about the applications, facilities and services available, their functioning and access modes. The Central Hub will also manage the E-RIHS ERIC web portal and host the European Grant Office providing support to heritage scientists looking for information about joining EU projects by, for example, sharing information about calls for proposals, research initiatives, and existing projects.
2. *The International Relations Unit* will be mainly devoted to science diplomacy activity. It will support institutional actors operating in heritage science to address common problems (e.g. political, institutional and administrative fragmentation) and build constructive international partnerships to strengthen the heritage science community worldwide.
3. *The Communication Unit* will be in charge of keeping the relationships with the heritage science community and the external public. It will manage social media outreach and other dissemination activities, including conferences and dissemination of related materials, news, meetings among stakeholders and so on.

At the second level there are the National Hubs, which operate at national level in diverse legal frameworks and represent the E-RIHS ERIC Member States. The National Hubs coordinate the national (and regional) providers; the latter are the entities that ultimately deliver the services to users. Activities of National Hubs include: giving access to research facilities, expertise and data; contributing to educational and training initiatives; organizing events and carrying out consultancy activities related to heritage. These activities will be performed under the E-RIHS ERIC label either as in-kind contributions or on the facility own initiative with E-RIHS ERIC agreement. National Hubs will be represented by the National Coordinators Committee in charge of ensuring coherence and consistency between in the scientific purposes and access policies, including the level of in-kind contributions by the Member States. The Committee will also contribute to design the scientific strategy of E-RIHS ERIC and monitoring its policies implementation.

At the strategic level, the E-RIHS ERIC General Assembly will be the highest and ultimate governing body with full decision-making power in terms of guidelines to be pursued in terms of new members, funding, quality control and other regulatory decisions. **The Director General** is appointed to execute decisions of the general assembly, while the **E-RIHS ERIC Advisory Board** will play the role of evaluating the scientific, technical and general activities of E-RIHS ERIC and providing the ethical assessment. The Advisory board is also expected to embrace representatives of users/researchers to provide with feedbacks on their research needs. Figure 4 illustrates the governance structure of E-RIHS ERIC.

²⁶ i.e. the "operations level" in "E-RIHS ERIC. Scientific and Technical Description. Draft 31.10.2018"

²⁷ See for details "E-RIHS ERIC. Central Activities. Draft 31.10.2018" and "E-RIHS ERIC. Scientific and Technical Description. Draft 31.10.2018"

Figure 4. Governance structure of E-RIHS ERIC

Source: "E-RIHS ERIC. Scientific and Technical Description. Draft 31.10.2018" p. 14, 15

As far as the funding mechanism is concerned, the sustainability of E-RIHS ERIC is guaranteed by a flexible funding structure based on in-cash and in-kind contributions. In-cash contributions come from Member States, which will pay an annual fee based on a percentage share of their GDP covering the operational costs of the E-RIHS ERIC governance structure. In-kind contributions, mainly from providers of services, consist of making available personnel (man-days), services (e.g. machine-time) or goods (e.g. a given number of access days to physical equipment, digital data, and so on) to E-RIHS ERIC users on the basis of previous (access) agreements between the ERIC and providers of facilities. The main types of in-kind contributions are described below. Beyond in-kind contributions from E-RIHS ERIC service catalogue, additional sources may come from transnational funding sources, sponsors and donors, as well as organisations that commission E-RIHS ERIC research and expertise.

2.4 Services

The list of services that E-RIHS ERIC will make available to users is defined by its catalogue and can be grouped in four categories. They are:

1. **Transnational access to physical facilities through three integrated platforms.** Platforms are integrated in the sense that E-RIHS ERIC will provide a single access point to one or more of them under a unified management structure that will ensure the coherence of the access (i.e. effectively assigning the right tools and modality of access to the users' research needs) and assistance during the access concerning the use of the equipment and interpretations of results²⁸. The platforms are:
 - ARCHLAB (ARCHive LABoratory) is a network of archives and will give access to (mostly unpublished) information and cultural heritage data accumulated in the past and preserved in archives of European museums and galleries (e.g. the British Museum and the National Gallery in London, the Prado museum in

²⁸ see "E-RIHS ERIC. Scientific and Technical Description. Draft 31.10.2018" for details

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- Madrid) and research institutions (e.g. the Centre for Research and Restoration of the Museums of France in Paris, the Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage in Brussels, Opificio delle Pietre Dure in Florence);
- FIXLAB (FIXed LABoratory) will give access to a network of large-scale and medium-scale facilities such as particle accelerators (e.g. the new AGLAE in Paris), synchrotrons (SOLEIL- IPANEMA in Paris), neutron sources (e.g. Budapest Neutron Centre) and other non-transportable analytical instruments for scientific investigations on samples or whole cultural heritage objects to analyse their microstructure and chemical composition, genesis of materials, and phenomena such as alteration and degradation;
 - MOLAB (Mobile LABoratory) will give access to bundle of mobile instrumentation for non- invasive measurements and complex diagnostics (Raman, UV-Vis fluorescence time-decay, optical coherence tomography, and so on) on immovable objects, archaeological sites and historical monuments. MOLAB arises from the necessity to carried in-situ examination for immovable cultural heritage objects (e.g. monuments, sculptures, buildings) and for movable patrimony (e.g. paintings, ceramics, gems, manuscripts, etc.) that is difficult, if not impossible, to move due to high risks and costs connected with their transportation and fragile state.
2. **Digital access to cultural heritage data through DIGILAB (DIGital LABoratory), which will represent the fourth integrated platform of E-RIHS ERIC and build under the IPERION HS project.** The main objective of DIGILAB is to give virtual access to data and making them FAIR (Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reusable). Cultural heritage data include digitalised resources (e.g. scanned artefacts), born-digital collections, attached metadata, annotations and further enrichments from an academic research and heritage institutions. Box 1 provides an example on how DIGILAB, along the FAIRness of data, is expected to work.²⁹
 3. **Education and training through E-RIHS Academy.** E-RIHS ERIC is expected to coordinate a comprehensive program of educational activities with the main goal of developing cross-disciplinary research skills. The program will include a mix of events such as training camps (i.e. courses about hands-on experience on the functioning of its platforms); summer schools (with more emphasis on theoretical and technical lectures in the field of heritage science), users' meetings and workshops (with the aim to share and discuss the results raising from the TNA and digital access experience as well as tracking and documenting the skills, knowledge and experience gained beyond the initial access and training);
 4. **Ancillary services such as the EU Grant Office, research pool and outreach activities** via publications and social networks. As mentioned above, the Central Hub will host a European Grant Office that will provide support to researchers' by sharing information about calls for proposals, research initiatives, and so on. E-RIHS ERIC will not grant research projects. Research pool and outreach activities include, e.g. sharing work in progress conference materials, news, meetings for stakeholders to discuss topics of

²⁹ Key elements of this environment would include conditions of access and reuse (e.g. license information) for each collection or object registered in the heritage data reuse charter. These elements are currently under discussion.

interest (e.g. development of heritage policies) and citizens' engagement via social networks and media.

Box 1. Example of DIGILAB structure and functioning

Rationale: Research e-infrastructures, digital archives and data services have become important pillars of scientific research that in recent decades has become ever more collaborative, distributed and data-intensive. Although the heritage science research community already adopts digital tools for data acquisition and analysis, the provision of e-infrastructure and services for data sharing, discovery, access and (re-)use have lagged behind.³⁰ This situation is being addressed by DIGILAB, an e-infrastructure that enables E-RIHS ERIC providers to supply access to their resources (datasets, collections) through the DIGILAB data portal, facilitating discovery, access and other services across the integrated platforms and resources. An example illustrating how DIGILAB is expected to work is provided below. The example illustrates the case of a user (e.g. a researcher) interested in carrying out a Raman analysis of the blue pigment used by Vincent van Gogh.

The FAIRness principle applied to heritage data. The effectiveness and usefulness of DIGILAB for the heritage science community relies on the extent data will be FAIR. Given a research query, e.g. *“Raman analysis of the blue pigment used by V. van Gogh”*, the FAIRness of data³¹ requires that the data would be:

- Findable, i.e. DIGILAB should be able to search for the key words of the query (e.g. Raman, analysis, pigment, blue, van Gogh) in all the databases whatever the language of the query and also for similar or incomplete words (e.g. Ram, pigm, etc). Therefore, the discovery of data with machine readable metadata concerns the verticality of the scheme, from the query to single service providers;
- Accessible, i.e. available and obtainable for users and machines that demand them. Heritage data should be shared under open license whenever possible, taking into account existing copyright and any restrictions due to e.g. privacy issues;
- Interoperable. Providers and institutions are asked to share their data in compliance with international standards and interoperability protocols. Data in DIGILAB are required to be syntactically analysable and semantically understandable. This allows data exchange and reuse among scientific heritage science disciplines, researchers, institutions and organisations. Interoperability, hence, deals with the horizontality of the scheme, where providers (and platforms) are asked to use compatible frameworks and interoperability protocols;
- Reusable, i.e. sufficiently described and shared with the least restrictive licenses. DIGILAB should provide heritage data, interpreted research results, visualisations of research outputs allowing the widest reuse possible (both in download and upload) across scientific disciplines and geographical borders.

Source: authors. The example was provided by the E-RIHS ERIC management during an interview.

2.5 Access policy

In line with the purpose of each service and users it is targeted to (see the CBA Annex for a detailed analysis of users), E-RIHS ERIC will offer customised modalities of access. At the time of writing, the following access options are being discussed:

- **Excellence-driven access** is the modality of access to physical platforms (ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB). The access is primarily addressed to the scientific research community (e.g. academics) in heritage science, and therefore to researchers involving in both “hard” and “soft” sciences. The target group includes both internal staff of providers and external users enabling trans-national collaborations, among the two groups of users. Excellence-driven access is exclusively dependent on scientific excellence, originality, team composition in terms of expertise, and technical feasibility of research proposals. A peer review from an external panel will evaluate the scientific quality of applications. To guarantee a wide participation of researchers within the heritage science scientific community, the

³⁰ Dillon et al. (2014); Katrakazis et al. (2018)

³¹ For a formal definition of FAIR see GO-FAIR, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>; and Wilkinson, Dumontier, and Mons (2016). <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

application process will be free of charge and not restricted to E-RIHS ERIC member countries. E-RIHS ERIC will prioritise investigations on publicly owned cultural and scientific collections, artefacts, objects, samples and monuments that are common heritage for all citizens.³²

- **Wide Access is the modality of access conceived for DIGILAB.** In line with the ‘Open Science’ priority of the European Commission in research and innovation policy³³ and to contribute to building a wide scientific community, E-RIHS ERIC will make DIGILAB accessible through a wide access policy, with some restrictions for copyright and privacy reasons.³⁴ Datasets registered in DIGILAB catalogue and stored in local repositories may belong to one of the following categories:
 - *Open Access Dataset* (e.g. accessible to anonymous users);
 - *Open Access to Registered Users Dataset*;
 - *Restricted-Access Dataset*, for registered users who have received permission from the data owner or repository manager;
 - *Dataset with Restricted-Access Data*, for registered users, with the exclusion of restricted access dataThe wide access will make DIGILAB a useful platform not only for researchers but also for other actors in the heritage science whose primary activity is not related to research but who would need scientific evidence and information on suitable facilities, making their job easier, more effective, and efficient.
- **Access to training and educational activities is regulated through the screening of the candidate applications** based on CVs, merits, motivation and educational background. While summer schools are designed for potential users of the transnational access program, i.e. post-graduate and PhD students, post-docs, conservators-restorers and scientists working in conservation and restoration of cultural heritage; training camps aimed at professionals in the field of heritage science (either individuals or teams from public and/or private institutions) who are interested in approaching and developing studies on conservational and analytical problems.

2.6 Objectives

E-RIHS ERIC is expected to face the challenges the heritage science community is currently dealing with by primarily pursuing three objectives³⁵:

1. **Giving to the heritage science community a common identity, fostering its integration and cohesion by creating a collaborative and multidisciplinary network,** simultaneously reducing existing distances among different scientific cultures, and

³² Privately owned artworks will be accepted only in some specific cases (“Excellence-driven access” in “E-RIHS PP. D.5.1 Users strategy and access policy”), while in any case Excellence-driven access must not amount to a commercial authentication service.

³³ The European Commission underlines the importance of ‘broad access to scientific publications and data to build on previous research results, encourage collaboration and avoid duplication of effort, speed up innovation and involve citizens and society through an improved transparency of the scientific process’ (EC, 2017). http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

³⁴ See the document “E-RIHS PP. D.5.1 Users strategy and access policy. Version 1.3, 31.01.2019”

³⁵ Authors’ formulation based on objectives stated in the E-RIHS ERIC Statute, Draft 15.02.2018

unconnected working methods and research practises. The aim is to create a cohesive and integrated heritage science community with advanced multidisciplinary and technological skills to innovate and progress in the study of heritage. Putting together researchers in SSH and STEM subjects with curators, conservationists, and policy makers is likely to make such a goal within reach.

2. Promoting the advancement in heritage science research offering Trans-National Access (TNA) to state-of-the-art physical and digital research facilities and services.

The aim is to enhance scientific quality of heritage science research by developing protocols, standards and procedure facilitating its cross-disciplinary approach to research questions and develop scientific and technological expertise for a better understanding of cultural heritage. The E-RIHS ERIC design in terms of legal status, geographical scope and functional features is designed to facilitate the access to a wide range of cutting-edge scientific infrastructures, expertise, methodologies, data and tools through its catalogue of services, with the goal of fostering technical and procedural innovations in the field, developing researchers' skills and knowledge, and ultimately enhancing scientific production.

3. Fostering interinstitutional research collaboration by managing the TNA and other E-RIHS ERIC services in a coordinated and integrated way through a single access point and a unified access regulation under the umbrella of a unique governance structure.

E-RIHS ERIC is expected to provide access to facilities located in different institutes (e.g. archives in museums) all over Europe reducing the negative impact on research of administrative barriers linked to heterogeneous legislation and overriding potential lack of agreements between institutions.

Thus, the key rationale for E-RIHS is mainly to make easier and cheaper the access to existing facilities and services by removing cultural, administrative and managerial barriers. In doing so, E-RIHS contributes to creating and shaping scientific networks and a community with a well-defined identity in the HS.

This is confirmed by the expectations expressed by the surveyed stakeholders, e.g. providers and national coordinators. Providers were asked their level of agreement about what was the added value of providing their services through the IPERION CH network (the prototype of E-RIHS ERIC) rather than as a stand-alone provider (Figure 5) Out of 13 providers³⁶, the great majority pointed to an increase of skills and research capacity because of a better exploitation of facilities (80%) also thanks to more challenging and of better-quality projects (70%). 80% of providers also agreed that IPERION CH increased their transnational research network, which allowed them to had additional users exploiting the access capacity of their facilities (70%). Based on the IPERION CH experience, they were also asked their expectations about joining E-RIHS ERIC (Figure 6). Most of providers expect to improve the network and increase their transnational collaborations even more, increase the number of users, and competencies thanks to more demanding projects.

³⁶ They represent more than 50% of the IPERION CH providers, which were 24.

Figure 5. The value added of offering services through IPERION CH

Source: CSIL survey to providers, Q.6. The number of valid questionnaires is equal to 13

Figure 6. Providers' expectations about joining E-RIHS ERIC

Source: CSIL survey to providers, Q.7. The number of valid questionnaires is equal to 13

The added value of having joined IPERION CH and the perceived impact of joining E-RISH ERIC was also investigated from the perspective of the national coordinators, i.e. from the member State viewpoint (15 valid questionnaires). National Coordinators unanimously agreed that E-RIHS ERIC will permit to achieve excellence in research through standardised protocols and peer-reviewed access to facilities, and contribute to build a transitional scientific community (Figure 7). Most of them also agreed that E-RIHS is likely to further increase interdisciplinarity (93%), reduce the amount of effort to coordinate national providers (87%), and help design a national strategy in Heritage Science (87%). Less than half sample (40%) believed that E-RIHS will contribute to create job in heritage science related sectors.

Figure 7. National Coordinators' expectations about joining E-RIHS ERIC

Source: CSIL survey to National Coordinators, Q.2. The number of valid questionnaires is equal to 15

2.7 Mapping of E-RIHS ERIC target users

To further enrich the picture of E-RIHS and identify the target population it refers to, a survey to its users of existing similar projects and potential ones was launched in the period from December 2018 to February 2019 (details are presented in Annex II of the accompanying report). 164 valid questionnaires were collected from respondents based in 32 different countries. Most of them were from Italy (35%, n=57), the UK (9%, n=15), Spain, Sweden, and Germany (6%, respectively), and from France (5%).

Figure 8. E-RIHS target users working institutions

Source: CSIL Survey to the E-RIHS target users, Q2. A.2.

The majority of respondents (62%) worked in academia, followed by those affiliated in institutes operating in the cultural and tourism sector such as museums and galleries (13%) (Figure 8). Figure 9 shows that researchers (in academia and non-academia) represent the lion share

(77%)³⁷, while the remaining share of 27% consisted of professionals who occupied different positions as directors and managers, restores, conservators, and technicians in cultural heritage institutions (e.g. museums, galleries, NGOs, and foundations) and in both private laboratories and within the public administration.

Figure 9. E-RIHS target users: main types of professions

Source: CSIL Survey to the E-RIHS target users. Pie on the left-hand side is from our elaboration on Q2. A.2, while the pie on the right-hand side is from Q3. A. 3. and Q4. A.4. “Researchers (academia and non-academia)” are individuals who identified themselves as researchers, professors, research assistant, Ph.D. and students, working in academic and non-academic institutions. “Professionals” are all the other respondents.

Respondents almost equally distribute as working on research fields belonging to STEM disciplines (30%), in SSH related subjects (28%), and in interdisciplinary sciences (26%) such as conservation and restoration sciences (Figure 10). Researchers (mainly physicians, chemists, and material scientists) particularly dominate in STEM disciplines;³⁸ while researchers and professionals coexist in interdisciplinary sciences and work in public and private institutions (e.g. museums and laboratories). As final point, it is worth noting that only 16% of respondents stated to work on Heritage Science matters, confirming that this more general domain still lacks a well-defined identity and that stakeholders do not perceived it as a stand-alone field of science yet. As mentioned above, the survey to the E-RIHS target users covered both the users of services provided by E-RIHS predecessors' projects and non-users, i.e. those people belonging to the heritage science community, but who have never accessed the E-RIHS' predecessors facilities. The reason for non-use is either because they did not know the existence of such projects or because they were aware of this possibility but had never applied to access. In this report, we refer to non-users as ‘E-RIHS potential users’ and in our survey, they represent 46% (75) of respondents.

³⁷According to Katrakazis et al. (2018), researchers in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) have produced or co-produced 80% of the Heritage Science literature in the last 20 years.

³⁸ Other evidence in this direction are in Dillon et al. (2014). Moreover, an analysis of publications related to E-RIHS predecessors' projects confirms this trend. Indeed, many publications are in journals such as “Microchemical Journal”, “Applied Surface Science”, “Journal of Radioanalytical and Nuclear Chemistry”.

Figure 10. Distribution of research fields among E-RIHS target users.

Source: CSIL survey to the E-RIHS target users, Q.5 A.5. Details are in Annex II.

Potential users were asked to what extent the set of statements reported in Figure 11 apply to their work or research activity. Most of the potential users seem to be already familiar with data and services they need for their research or work (71%), but the lack of information and skills prevent them from using new data and facilities. Only 42% of them are used to not collaborating while doing research or work and only 34% are able to cover the cost of carrying out research. This points to that collaboration is crucial and costs represent a clear financial barrier for heritage science scientists.

Figure 11. E-RIHS potential users needs and challenges in research.

Source: CSIL survey to the E-RIHS target users, Q.63 F.1 Apply groups 'totally', 'to a large extent', and 'fairly'; Do Not Apply groups 'Not really', 'Not at all', 'N/A.'

As a final point, potential users were asked whether they were interested in using the services provided by E-RIHS ERIC. The large majority (76%) expressed their interest (Figure 12) and identify the accessibility to data, archives and other physical facilities for analysis of cultural heritage as well as the opportunity to set up international and multi-disciplinary research collaboration as the main ways E-RIHS could help improve their work (Table 2)³⁹.

³⁹ Accompanying report, Annex II Q65 F.3 for the full answers.

Figure 12. E-RIHS potential users' interest in the project

Source: CSIL survey to E-RIHS target users, Q.64 F.2. Full question: "E-RIHS is a platform that operates in heritage science (heritage interpretation, preservation, documentation and management). It offers access to physical labs, collections/archives, mobile instrumentation and virtual data in a coordinated manner via a single access point. Would you be interested in using such a platform?"

Table 2. How could E-RIHS ERIC help you improve your research/work?

Quotes
"Make recent studies and publication accessible and sharable"
"Networking with others, access to analytical equipment, sharing skills and knowledge"
"To make an easy and cheaper habit to work with other institutions"
"A quick comparison of a wide range of data shared which the scientific community will surely help to improve research and application of good practices in conservation and management"
"More opportunities for collaboration; access to equipment not available in-house"
"Through better possibilities of finding collaborations to search for answers to research questions together with those with a similar interest, as well as through access to expensive instruments and expertise".

Source: CSIL survey to the E-RIHS target users, Q65 F.3. This is an open-ended question addressed to E-RIHS potential users.

Taken together, the evidence from the surveys suggests that a potential demand for E-RIHS ERIC services is likely to exist legitimising the enlargement of the array of services, the number of providers, and Member States with respect to preceding projects. Moreover, the alignment between providers' and (non-)users' expectations indicates that E-RIHS ERIC is expected to generate a benefit for both parties: providers are likely to reduce potential inefficiencies arising from a sub-optimal exploitation of their facilities while enhancing the quality of their research; users will enjoy the access to facilities, data, and knowledge as well as increase their collaboration opportunities to improve their own research.

3. Logic Model: a way of thinking about the E-RIHS ERIC impacts

The impact assessment exercise has been guided by a logic model (Figure 13). It illustrates the causal chain that connects *Challenges* in the heritage science to E-RIHS ERIC *Objectives* and *Impacts*, both direct and wider impacts. Via the resources cash and in-kind (*Inputs*) that Members States and providers channel into E-RIHS ERIC, the latter offers TNAs to physical facilities and remote access to digital platforms, training and outreach activities (*Core activities*) with the aim of giving to the heritage science community a common identity, advance in heritage science research and overcoming obstacles to inter-institutional research collaboration (*Objectives*). The know-how from previous projects is another important input contributing to the future development of E-RIHS ERIC activities. This logic model can be the basis for future monitoring and evaluation activities, on the basis of a well-identified list of Key Performance Indicators (KPI). The full list of KPI is reported in the CBA Annex in the accompanying report and they are classified by main impact categories: science production; human capital and development; and dissemination and outreach.

The Cost Benefits Analysis quantifies the **direct impacts** E-RIHS ERIC is expected to produce on the heritage science community by identifying and forecasting (along the entire time horizon) the number of users who directly benefit from each E-RIHS ERIC activity (*Output*). This output is further elaborated to obtain *Outcomes*, i.e. the monetisation of the benefits accruing to the scientific community

Based on this framework, the expected direct impacts on heritage science community can be summarised as follow:

1. Impact on science production

E-RIHS ERIC will enable the heritage science community to enhance their research performance in terms efficiency (e.g. time savings) and quality by facilitating access and providing related information (e.g. help desks) to state-of-the art physical and digital infrastructure including fresh and interoperable information (**scientific information and access**). This, in turn, could lead to increasing production and quality of publications (**knowledge creation**). In doing so, activities of E-RIHS ERIC are expected to contribute to build a heritage science community and enhance its cohesion and integration by representing it under a common label and contributing to produce common research practices thanks to multidisciplinary and interinstitutional research collaboration.

2. Impact on human capital development

E-RIHS Academy will deliver face-to-face lectures and training to enhance skills in the use of facilities and disseminate knowledge including collaborating activities among researchers and operators from different institutions and disciplines and, hence, boosting cross-fertilisation in heritage science.

3. Dissemination and outreach

The dissemination and outreach activities of E-RIHS ERIC Central Hub (via social networks and E-RIHS ERIC web pages) will enable **to promote the heritage science and its social role** in understanding and preserving the cultural heritage beyond the scientific community reaching the general public.

In addition to direct impact, indirect impacts may further expand and generate benefits beyond the scientific community to **citizens, firms and policy makers**. The chain from direct to wider impacts is long, non-linear and depends on whether some enabling conditions occur. Their occurrence is influenced both by internal factors to E-RIHS ERIC and external conditions dealing with different stakeholders. The qualitative socio-economic impact assessment provides insights on how wider impacts may materialise and what are the conditioning factors. Two main wider impacts have been identified in this report:

1. Science diplomacy and impact on cultural policies

As a global actor in heritage science, E-RIHS ERIC ambition is to contribute to build a cultural identity at a national and international level as well as act in science and cultural diplomacy, producing soft power outcomes on bilateral and international relations. This holds true as much as E-RIHS ERIC will be able to build a strong heritage science community identity and as much as the global reach of E-RIHS ERIC activities is achieved. Its inclusion in the GSO as well as its collaboration with ICCROM are paving the way to that.

2. Impact on access to culture and on cultural tourism.

Research supported by E-RIHS ERIC in conservation, restoration and archiving may be used for scientific dissemination, training activities for non-specialist public, and making inaccessible or endangered cultural heritage accessible. Outreach activities for the general public can enhance citizens' awareness on the heritage science role by providing them with non-technical knowledge and understanding of artistic and cultural assets, including those with potential touristic interest. The artefacts restored thanks to E-RIHS ERIC or innovation processes in museums and cultural sites favoured by the research infrastructure may enhance the way in which citizens' access and interact with heritage and, as a result, stimulate the cultural tourism. These technological developments can be further exploited downstream by operators such as touristic services and industry for the construction of new communication tools targeted to visitors. For this impact to be realised, additional resources mobilised and investments made by firms are necessary, as well as a closer connection between the heritage science community and the firms operating in the touristic and cultural sector.

Figure 13. E-RIHS ERIC CBA and socio-economic impact evaluation logic model

4. Assumptions

Based on the understanding described in the previous sections, the analysis assessed the nature and magnitude of E-RIHS ERIC impact. A number of assumptions and working hypotheses underpin the analysis, especially the CBA, and they are described in this chapter.

4.1 Time horizon: a long-term perspective

The impact assessment takes a long-term perspective. Since the project is currently in the preparatory phase it is important that sufficient data are generated regarding the future evolution of activities and services in order to fully appreciate its impacts.

Figure 14. Timeline

Source: Authors

The time horizon of the CBA goes from 2017 (i.e. base year) to year 2057. Three phases can be highlighted in the time horizon:

- A 'set-up phase' which includes preparatory activities. It started in 2017⁴⁰ and will continue with IPERION HS in the period 2020-2022.⁴¹ Before 2017, IPERION CH (2015- 2019) paved the way for E-RIHS ERIC and is included within the scope of the project.
- A launch and start-up phase. It goes from 2023 to 2026 when E-RIHS ERIC will enter in the full regime after a ramp-up phase of three years (2023 – 2025).

⁴⁰ In 2017, the preparatory phase of E-RIHS ERIC (PP) started with an expected duration of three years (2017 – 2019). The European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Preparatory Phase (E-RIHS PP). <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/209507/factsheet/en>

⁴¹ IPERION HS (Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science) is a three-year project proposal expected to start at the end of IPERION CH until the starting of E-RIHS ERIC in 2023. To maximise the alignment with E-RIHS ERIC, divergences between IPERION HS and E-RIHS ERIC governing structures and functioning will be minimal, also involving the same partners as IPERION CH and E-RIHS PP.

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- The ‘operating phase’, going from 2026 to the end of the time horizon.

Adopting a long-time horizon has a double implication:

- Future values must be forecasted according to realistic considerations
- Future monetary flows are discounted through a social discount rate of 3% in real terms.

4.2 Counterfactual and the added value

The analysis adopts an incremental approach; i.e. compares a scenario with-the-project against a counterfactual scenario without-the-project. The ‘what if’ assumptions allow to calculate the net impact and thus to identify the added value of E-RIHS, that is to say, the net change in the world imputable to E-RIHS.

A peculiarity of E-RIHS is that its main rationale is to coordinate and improve the access to already existing facilities. This means that, in the absence of E-RIHS, most of its services and facilities would still be available in principle to the scientific community, but not in a coordinated and integrated way. For instance, IPANEMA⁴², based at the synchrotron SOLEIL, is a research platform operating under the umbrella of E-RIHS and it is entirely devoted to the study of ancient samples and artefacts. IPANEMA facilitates the access to FIXLAB via coordination activities such as easing contacts between specialists, co-preparing research proposals/applications, providing technical support (adapted sample environment, support to sample preparation, complementary analyses, data processing) and developing research methodologies in imaging and data analysis. In that case, although the situation without E-RIHS is to access SOLEIL via calls for applications managed directly by SOLEIL itself, the coordination and assistance offered by E-RIHS ERIC represent an added-value service otherwise not available to users. A similar example comes from instrumentation provided by MOLAB, whose equipment often includes “home-made” software exclusively developed for research in heritage science. Even though in the counterfactual scenario existing commercial tools were able to provide similar analysis, users of MOLAB can experience an added value from accessing MOLAB in terms of better results (e.g. more accurate measurements) which are likely to scale up their research. The added-value of E-RIHS is likely to increase when the access is not only coordinated (e.g. assistance when doing research, coordination of different expertise) but also integrated, i.e. when E-RIHS facilitates the access to multiple platforms or facilities which are complementary to each other (see below).

The level of coordination and integration along with the type of service determine the added value E-RIHS ERIC will generate for its users and a continuum of circumstances may materialise. To make this concept simple and manageable, this report distinguishes four broad cases reflecting four magnitudes of added value.⁴³ Each impact is associated with a specific counterfactual scenario (Table 3):

1. The first case applies if E-RIHS ERIC will not differentiate from existing services/facilities and its added value would be very small or nil. For instance, synchrotrons have often a well-structured access policy and providing access to users is their core activity. Without any form of coordination or integrating activity, users could access them at the same

⁴² European Institute for the non-destructive photon-based analysis of ancient materials. <http://ipanema.cnrs.fr>

⁴³ The four cases are based on insights from interviews and surveys.

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- conditions (same costs) and achieving the same research results (same benefits) with or without E-RIHS.
2. The second case is a circumstance where users could in principle access facilities at the same conditions (same costs) but the intermediation of E-RIHS ERIC would create an added value in terms of improvement of the research quality thanks to customised services to the applicants (higher benefits). Suppose for instance, an integrated access, through which the user can access e.g. to multiple synchrotrons affiliated to a single platform such a FIXLAB. Although the access via E-RIHS would be still in compliance with the access policy of each synchrotron (same cost), the added value of E-RIHS ERIC would emerge from providing expertise, and advising the appropriate technology tailored to user's research needs, and therefore likely increasing research quality.
 3. The third case describes a situation where the facilities would be in principle accessible in a scenario without E-RIHS ERIC, but the existence of barriers (administrative and financial obstacles, lack of information and skills by the users, full exploitation of the machine, and so on) restrict, somehow, the accessibility. For instance, starting from the user research project, ARCHLAB coordinates different archives in Europe with the aim of delivering the necessary information and expertise to the user to carry out her/his research project. This service would be not available in a counterfactual scenario where the user should look for disseminated, spread-out, and perhaps unpublished data (given that users exactly know what they are looking for). In that case, E-RIHS ERIC would improve access conditions (lower costs) and increase the probability of performing additional experiments and research (higher benefits).
 4. The added value of E-RIHS is likely to reach its maximum when it provides not existing services (e.g. access to otherwise non-accessible archives, or university labs' equipment) or coordination and integration services which are unique making it the sole research infrastructure able to accommodate certain types of research (benefits). For example, an integrated and coordinated access can ensure the use of multiple facilities affiliated to a single platform as described above, but also the access to multiple providers in one or more platforms such as FIXLAB + ARCHLAB). Indeed, and depending on the type of research, the services ARCHLAB, MOLAB, FIXLAB offer are complementary to each other and each one adds a piece of valuable information to the research project.

Hence, E-RIHS is justified as long as the access it enables is more efficient than in the absence of it (higher cost in terms of time and skills to access would be needed) or the extent it reduces barriers to access, which currently discourage scientists to actively apply for access, thus potentially reducing the scientific quality of their work. Question B.10 of the survey to the E-RIHS target users asked them to what extent the access to services provided by any of E-RIHS predecessors⁴⁴ had changed efficiency in doing research/work (time saved compared to if no such services existed). Most of the respondents (76%) indicated a time saving, while only 32% indicated no change (or negative change).⁴⁵ Similarly, the question B.11 asked whether in absence of E-RIHS predecessor projects these services would have been available from other sources. Again, 76% of respondents answered that they could not have used such or similar services.

⁴⁴ IPERION CH, Eu-ARTECH, CHARISMA, ARIADNE

⁴⁵ The negative change can derive from training with unfamiliar services and data before using them.

Table 3 visualises the conceptualisation of the E-RIHS ERIC added value with respect to a scenario without it. Column 1 reports the magnitude of the impact, Column 2 the associated costs and benefits, while Column 3 shows the theoretical added value for each magnitude of the impact. The latter is quantified in the CBA Annex by using ‘efficiency gain coefficients’: the more integrated and coordinated the service offered (thus the effect in terms of decreasing the cost of access), the higher the efficiency gain in terms of avoided costs (either time or financial cost savings) generated by E-RIHS ERIC. Of course, the added value is also maximum when E-RIHS permits the access to otherwise non accessible facilities. The survey to providers asked them whether providing access to external users was part of their core activity: 50% answer ‘yes’, while the remaining 50% declared that their facility mainly carries out in-house research by scientific internal staff and providing external access is an ancillary activity. Moreover, only 50% of them have facilities entirely dedicated to heritage science, confirming the necessity of expanding the supply of services for heritage science scientists.⁴⁶

The time and costs saving experienced thanks to the access through E-RIHS is the efficiency gain reflecting the net impact of E-RIHS in the TNA access (via ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB) to already existing physical facilities. Beyond the calculation of the efficiency gain, the added value of E-RIHS is also linked to the number of users it will be able to attract. Accordingly, Column 4 reports the share of users by platform and by magnitude of the efficiency gain (see the section Demand Analysis below). For instance, most of FIXLAB users (60%) are expected to experience a small or nil impact because synchrotrons and particle accelerators would be accessible even in a counterfactual scenario without E-RIHS. FIXLAB users are likely to enjoy a high impact when the access is enriched by coordination (e.g. assistance for the logistic, expertise) and integrating activities (e.g. use of complementary technology from MOLAB platform). This would happen for 15% of FIXLAB users. In contrast, the majority of MOLAB users will benefit from a high impact because facilities would not be likely accessible otherwise.

Table 3. Counterfactual scenarios: the added value of E-RIHS ERIC

Net impact	Costs and benefits	Added value (ERIHS ERIC - Alternatives)	% of TNA users by type of impact		
			ARCHLAB	FIXLAB	MOLAB
Nil	$B_E = B_A$ $C_E = C_A$	$(B_E - C_E) - (B_A - C_A) = 0$	25%	60%	10%
Medium-low	$B_E > B_A$ $C_E = C_A$	$(B_E - C_E) - (B_A - C_A) = (B_E - B_A) = X > 0$	10%	15%	15%
Medium-high	$B_E > B_A$ $C_E < C_A$	$(B_E - C_E) - (B_A - C_A) = Y > X$	50%	10%	60%
High	$B_{EI} > B_A$ $C_E < C_A$	$(B_{EI} - C_E) - (B_A - C_A)$ $Z > Y$	15%	15%	15%
TOTAL			100%	100%	100%

Source: authors based on survey data and interviews. B_E = benefits of E-RIHS ERIC; B_{EI} = benefits of E-RIHS ERIC generated by an integrated access; B_A = benefits of alternatives; C_E = costs of E-RIHS ERIC; C_A = costs of alternatives.

In the case of DIGILAB, the added value of E-RIHS would be to make available FAIR data to the heritage science community. The added value of accessing FAIR data has been documented by

⁴⁶ See the accompanying report, Annex II, Question 3 and Question 4 of the survey to providers.

several studies,⁴⁷ including some in the field of heritage science.⁴⁸ Positive impacts are mainly expected in terms of reducing effort in research in terms of time to collect or/and recreate already existing data as well as scaling up research findings and quality based on integrated data from multiple disciplines (see CBA Annex for details).

All other services (e.g. training, web portal, events and dissemination activities) are considered to be new as compared to a situation without E-RIHS, so in this case the counterfactual is a 'do nothing' scenario, i.e. the impact of these greenfield services is entirely attributable to E-RIHS.

4.3 Scenarios

When projecting future values, it is always sensible to consider the inherent uncertainty of the exercise. For this reason, three scenarios (pessimistic, baseline and optimistic) have been identified to forecast future costs and benefits. A scenario analysis is then performed to assess how the alternative future developments of E-RIHS can impact on its future performance. A conservative approach has been adopted to counteract possible optimism biases.

The cost-book⁴⁹ of E-RIHS ERIC lists the values that costs and other variables used to calculate benefits (e.g. the number of users) take on in the pessimistic and optimistic scenarios with respect to the baseline scenario. Scenarios were discussed in depth with the E-RIHS ERIC management with the project partners at several meetings. In the next sections costs and benefits (impact) are always presented for the three scenarios.

4.4 Demand analysis

The success of E-RIHS ERIC depends on factors determining both the supply side of the heritage science (research) market and its demand. The realisation of the infrastructure (e.g. the Central Hub, DIGILAB) and the establishment of a pan-European network to facilitate the access to an increasing number of leading facilities and expertise is not a sufficient condition to attract a large number of users. Indeed, it is necessary that this expansion of supply of services is supported by a potential demand. **The demand analysis of E-RIHS ERIC is the attempt to estimate the number of future users of E-RIHS ERIC.**

E-RIHS ERIC is expected to support the use and sharing of instrumentation, data and skills for research in heritage interpretation, preservation, documentation and management. Such a vast scope is likely to attract diverse potential users, including those from cultural heritage institutions, cultural heritage labs, researchers, academic institutions, and public policy services as suggested by the users' mapping analysis shown above. More importantly, the mapping analysis also reveals the existence of an excess of demand with respect to the current level of

⁴⁷ EC (2018); Tenopir (2011); Parson, Grimshaw and Williamson (2013)

⁴⁸ See for instance Dariah annual reports.

⁴⁹ The Cost Book of E-RIHS ERIC was jointly developed by CSIL and the E-RIHS ERIC management and validated by its Scientific Advisory Board (SAB). The Cost Book reports the value of unitary fixed costs of the Central Hub (the cost of maintaining the headquarter and personal costs), unitary variable costs such as the costs of conferences, summer schools, and training camps, and the monetisation of the in-kind contributions (e.g. the value of the machine-time, man-days, etc.).

supply. 46% of survey respondents were non-users but they would be ready to access E-RIHS' services if more information about the facilities, necessary skills on how to use them, and modes of access was conveyed.

The user's forecasts considered in this study rely on indication from the surveys, observable evidence from IPERION CH concerning both its level of demand and the unitary cost of access, consultation with E-RIHS ERIC management, interviews with managers of research infrastructures, and secondary data from academic and grey literature. Pessimistic and optimistic scenarios and the risk analysis to address forecast errors have been also carried out to take into consideration the possible uncertainty of the estimates, which mainly stems from the extent E-RIHS will be able to intercept the potential demand.

The categories of users considered in the CBA are: users of platforms ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB; users of the E-RIHS ERIC web portal; users of DIGILAB; users of educational and training activities; users of dissemination and outreach activities.⁵⁰ Table 4 shows the forecasts of the number of users per year accessing to physical platforms in the baseline, pessimistic and optimistic scenario respectively at full regime, i.e. from 2026 onwards. Details and main assumptions for the demand analysis are presented below; while the CBA Annex presents the forecasts of all other categories of users obtained as linear functions of the users of the physical platforms.

The pessimistic scenario reflects the actual situation of IPERION HS, a three-year 'bridge' project connecting the IPERION CH (which ends in 2019) and the starting phase of E-RIHS ERIC in 2023. It has a total of 52 providers (13 affiliated to ARCHLAB network, 23 to FIXLAB, and 16 to MOLAB), which are expected to host, on average, 500 users. On the basis of the average unit cost per day of access per single platform⁵¹ and considering 5 days of access per user, it was calculated that 40% (200) of users are absorbed by MOLAB, 30% (150) by ARCHLAB, and the remaining 30% (150) by ARCHLAB. The monetisation of the in-kind contribution was obtained by multiplying the number of users by the cost of access. In the pessimistic scenario, E-RIHS ERIC will cover the cost of travel and subsistence to 100 out of 500 users, whose research projects distinguish for their excellence. These costs will be supported by the users in the other cases. As far as the number of training events and conferences is concerned, 4 events are foreseen: 1 training camp, 1 summer school, 1 users meeting, and 1 conference in Europe. The amount of communication costs depends on the level of E-RIHS ERIC network development and outreach: in the pessimistic scenario it is expected to be 25% lower than the cost in the baseline scenario.⁵² Vice versa, the cost for the maintenance of DIGILAB is assumed to be the same regardless the scenario.

The demand analysis in the baseline scenario was carried out starting with the most likely number of providers expected to join E-RIHS ERIC by 2023; while the optimistic scenario reflects

⁵⁰ At the time of writing, the access policy does not foresee any access to private firms or users for marketed services (e.g. authentication of artworks). More details are provided in the CBA annex.

⁵¹ The cost of one day of access is as follows: EUR 260.42 per ARCHLAB, EUR 471.46 per FIXLAB, and EUR 735.11 per MOLAB. The cost of ARCHLAB is mainly calculated considering the cost of a man-day; MOLAB cost includes the cost of transportation and insurance of the machine and the personnel cost (man-day); while the cost of FIXLAB cover the cost of the machine-time and that of the personnel. See the Cost-book for details.

⁵² In the baseline scenario the communication-related costs amount to EUR 40,000 (source: Cost-Book).

the circumstance E-RIHS ERIC will expand beyond Europe, with an even higher number of providers.

Table 4. Main assumptions for the demand analysis in the three scenarios

ITEMS	Pessimistic	Baseline	Optimistic
TNA - Users per platform (N)	500	809	1,077
<i>ARCHLAB</i>	150	231	346
<i>FIXLAB</i>	150	228	293
<i>MOLAB</i>	200	350	438
TNA - users' distribution per platform (%)	100%	100%	100%
<i>ARCHLAB</i>	30%	29%	32%
<i>FIXLAB</i>	30%	28%	27%
<i>MOLAB</i>	40%	43%	41%
TNA -Providers per platform (N)	52	83	110
<i>ARCHLAB</i>	13	20	30
<i>FIXLAB</i>	23	35	45
<i>MOLAB</i>	16	28	35
TNA - Users per provider per platform (N)			
<i>ARCHLAB</i>	12	12	12
<i>FIXLAB</i>	7	7	7
<i>MOLAB</i>	13	13	13
TNA - Projects per provider per platform (N)			
<i>ARCHLAB</i>	4	4	4
<i>FIXLAB</i>	2	2	2
<i>MOLAB</i>	4	4	4
TNA - In-kind contribution per platform (EUR)	1,284,025	2,125,015	2,750,607
<i>ARCHLAB</i>	195,314	300,484	450,726
<i>FIXLAB</i>	353,598	538,084	691,822
<i>MOLAB</i>	735,113	1,286,447	1,608,059
ITEMS	Pessimistic	Baseline	Optimistic
N of users to whom E-RIHS will cover travel and subsistence	100	250	500
N of training events and conferences	4	6	9
N of Summer Schools	1	1	1
N of Training camps	1	1	1
N of User meetings	1	2	4
N of Conferences	1	2	3
in Europe	1	1	2
out of Europe	0	1	1
Communication (cost change compared to baseline)	-25%	0%	25%
DIGILAB (EUR cost per year)	30,000	30,000	30,000

5. Costs of E-RIHS ERIC

5.1 Investment costs

The total investment costs of E-RIHS ERIC (including costs incurred during the preparatory phase as well as the cost of IPERION CH which is part of the investment phase) **amount to EUR 20,675,839 (at 2017 prices).**

Table 5. Investment costs of E-RIHS ERIC

ITEM	Not discounted value EUR	Discounted value EUR 2017
IPERION CH*	8,157,488	8,162,382
E-RIHS PP*	3,999,449	3,999,449
IPERION HS**	8,454,000	7,513,457
TOTAL	21,616,382	20,675,839

Source: Not discounted values are from *European Commission, CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service); ** E-RIHS ERIC management. Constant values are from CSIL elaborations.

5.2 Operating costs

Operating costs are all the outlays needed to operate and maintain E-RIHS ERIC and include both in-kind and cash contribution as well as fixed items, i.e. they do not (or only marginally) vary when the size of activities changes (e.g. the operating costs of the Central Hub) and variable items. The source of operating costs is the cost-book of E-RIHS ERIC.

Table 6. Operating cost breakdown by main items in the baseline scenario (EUR).

OPERATING COSTS ITEM	TOTAL current (nominal) value EUR 2017	TOTAL Constant (real) value EUR 2017	Yearly operating costs at full regime
FIXED-COSTS (A)	45,885,000	24,299,470	1,311,000
Central-hub (personnel and travel expenses)	33,635,000	17,812,197	961,000
Digital infrastructure management and curation	3,500,00	1,853,506	100,000
Centrally funded investments	1,750,000	926,753	50,000
Other/contingency & emergency management	7,000,000	3,707,013	200,000
VARIABLE – COSTS (B)	17,193,750	9,105,351	491,250
Users travel and subsistence	7,568,750	4,008,208	216,250
Training, events, communication	9,625,000	5,097,143	275,000
SUBTOTAL - CASH (A+B)	63,078,750	33,404,821	1,802,250
IN-KIND (C)	11,550,000	6,116,571	330,000
DIGILAB	1,050,00	556,052	30,000
Central – hub (main building maintenance)	10,500,000	5,560,519	300,000
TOTAL (A+B+C)	74,628,750	39,521,392	2,132,250

Source: CSIL elaboration. Primary source: E-RIHS ERIC cost-book. Yearly values expressed in nominal terms.

Yearly operating costs, net of in-kind contributions by providers, **will amount at full regime to EUR 2,132,250**. Over the entire time horizon E-RIHS ERIS will have operating of EUR 39,521,392 (at 2017 prices).

It has to be noted that, in the counterfactual scenario, in-kind contributions from providers of ARCHLAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB are not accounted for because their access costs (i.e. machine or personnel time) would otherwise exist in a scenario without E-RIHS ERIC and therefore net costs would be zero.

6. Direct impacts

Against its investment and operating costs, E-RIHS ERIC produces an amount of benefits (positive impacts) which is worth **EUR 71,551,135 in present terms**. The main results are presented and commented in this section, while the technical details of estimations are included in the CBA Annex.

Table 7. E-RIHS ERIC total benefits in the baseline scenario (EUR 2017).

Impact / benefit	Constant (real) value, EUR 2017
Science production	65,873,325
Access	49,225,764
Publications	16,301,935
Scientific information	315,625
Human capital development	2,736,874
Value of training	2,736,874
Dissemination and outreach	2,940,936
E-RIHS ERIC web portal	2,682,913
Social networks	258,024
TOTAL BENEFITS	71,551,135

Source: CSIL elaboration.

Not surprisingly, **the science production accounts for 92.3% (EUR 65,873,325)** of the total value of E-RIHS ERIC impact. Being designed to primarily serve the scientific community in the field of heritage, E-RIHS is expected to increase its productivity by enabling a more efficient and effective access to existing excellent facilities, to information about their existence and use as well as the development of new advanced services in the form of availability of FAIR data (through DIGILAB) which ultimately may also translate into additional quality of publications.

Figure 15. Breakdown of E-RIHS ERIC benefits by main impact area, % on total.

Source: CSIL elaboration.

Science production impact embraces three different aspects:

- **The value of access** is the efficiency generated when accessing the E-RIHS ERIC platforms FIXLAB, ARCHLAB, MOLAB, and DIGILAB. It reflects the added value of coordination activities, including offering an (integrated and coordinated) access to a wide range of scientific instruments and methodologies for research advances in the cultural heritage and it is measured in terms of avoided costs. The value of FAIR data expected to be delivered by DIGILAB is encompassed as well and proxied by the efficiency gained in having ready to use quality data.
- **The value of publications (and citations)** is the second most important general benefit generated by E-RIHS ERIC. It accounts for 24.5% of the impact related to science production and it is measured in terms of the time spent to produce and, then, to use (i.e. read) the scientific publications prepared as a consequence of the access.
- **The value of scientific information** captures the benefit generated by the website of E-RIHS ERIC as “one-stop-shop point” where (potential) users can receive information, resolve doubts, and easily access the (virtual) front offices for all services. Such a benefit materialises before and regardless of the actual access and use of E-RIHS ERIC services and data. It is worth 0.5% of the impact associated with science production and, again, it is measured in terms of time-saving.

Focusing on the value of access, the lion share of the science production impact accounting for about 73% of it, it has to be noted that the highest share is given by the accessibility to FAIR data ensured by DIGILAB (54.5% of total access value), while TNA access to physical platforms accounts for 45.5% of total value of access. Here, MOLAB is the platform guaranteeing the highest share, with ARCHLAB and FIXLAB providing almost equal shares of the remaining impact. The highest share of MOLAB is mainly due to the absolute higher number of users as compared to FIXLAB and ARCHLAB, and the highest share of users experienced a ‘medium-high’ added value coefficient, which derives from the fact that MOLAB facilities and instrumentation would be difficult to access without E-RIHS.

Figure 16. Breakdown of E-RIHS ERIC science production impact by main categories, %.

Source: CSIL elaboration.

The impact on human capital development accounts for 3.7% (EUR 2,736,874) of the total E-RIHS ERIC impact value. It is a measure of the value of educational and training events delivered by the E-RIHS ERIC academy from the viewpoint of attendees. This can be proxied by the value in monetary terms of the travel cost and value of time spent by attendees joining the training events.

The dissemination and outreach impact covers a share of 4.0% and amounts to EUR 2,940,936. It consists of two components:

- the benefits generated to web portal visitors (net of potential web portal users for TNA access) which values EUR 2,682,913 (91.2% of the dissemination and outreach impact);
- The value generated by social networks (Facebook and Twitter). It amounts to EUR 258,024 and represent about 9% of the dissemination impact.

Here again, the monetisation of such an impact is done through the estimates of virtual visitors and estimation of the time spent to read news and information related to E-RIHS, which is assumed to be at least equal to the benefit visitors enjoy from the 'visit' or from reading the news.

Such estimates are clearly prone to risks since they rely on a number of assumptions related to the behaviour and preferences of scientists and other users of E-RIHS and their evolution over time. For this reason, sensitivity and risk analyses have been performed to identify the sources of risk and measure the impact on the final performance.

Based on the probabilistic risk analysis, and when comparing benefits of E-RIHS with its costs in a long-term perspective, it is estimated that there is a high probability (88%) that E-RIHS will bring positive net benefits to the society. The cost-benefit analysis points to a **baseline value of EUR 11.3 million, an economic rate of return of 6.02% and a B/C ratio of 1.20.**

The most critical aspects underlying the materialisation of the impacts, that is to say those likely to affect the most the final performance of E-RIHS, are the number of users, especially those of MOLAB, and the magnitude of the efficiency gains brought about by E-RIHS which increases as coordination and integration between platforms improves and also depends on the level of FAIRness of data in DIGILAB.

7. Wider impacts

Heritage science advances the understanding, interpretation, conservation, authentication and management of cultural heritage, both moveable and built. It has the potential to inform complex social problems, including climate adaptation strategies, moving beyond the understanding the value of cultural heritage to communities, health and well-being, or the contribution to national economies (Bell, 2015). Therefore, some areas of wider impact have been identified as further advancement to the direct impacts discussed in the previous chapters.

The following secondary non-measurable wider impacts project have been identified:

1. **Science diplomacy and impact on cultural policies.** These impacts can include both effects in terms of cultural identity at a national and European level as well as cultural diplomacy and soft power outcomes on bilateral and international relations. Institutional activities including participating in international conferences and events, as well as advocacy activities related to cultural activities and policies, may have positive impacts not only on cultural policies but also on broad international diplomatic relationships. This holds true in as much as the global reach of IPERION HS activities is achieved. The inclusion of E-RIHS in the GSO as well as its collaboration with ICCROM are paving the way to that.
2. **Impact on access to culture and on cultural tourism.** Tourist/access effects can derive from innovation processes in museums and cultural sites triggered by the knowledge and experience developed in the context of E-RIHS ERIC activities and further exploited downstream. They may take the form of design of new products and services to enrich the cultural offer, construction of new narratives and communication tools targeted to visitors, etc.

The areas of analysis mentioned above are different since they imply different target groups, pathways and conditions for materialisation. Therefore, for each area specific ‘storylines’ are discussed in the following chapters highlighting common traits to allow comparability and horizontal reading. In particular the analysis intends to:

1. Identify specific areas of potential wider impact through a literature review and interviews with experts;
2. Discuss how and to what extent E-RIHS may contribute to such impacts;
3. Analyse the conditions and pathways that led to the genesis and implementation of these desirable wider impacts, this also through a review of international cases and a sample of possible outcomes.

A specific example of wider impacts at the local level is the contribution of E-RIHS on its host city of Florence. This is discussed in a dedicated Annex.

7.1 Agenda Setting in Cultural Policies and Cultural Diplomacy

The objectives that E-RIHS sets in terms of improving the efficiency and scientific quality of heritage science research, the services offered and the distribution model of these services, make it possible for E-RIHS to become an important laboratory in terms of cultural policy making and agenda setting, with potential impacts also in related areas such as cultural diplomacy and cultural cooperation. Heritage science on the one hand, and policy makers on the other are looking at these areas with increasing attention, as confirmed by a review of recent literature

on heritage science, conservation studies and cultural policy, and from the analysis of some significant projects started over the last two decades⁵³.

As stated by Katrakazis et. al "heritage science does not contribute to cultural value in isolation, but rather through its interaction with a diverse network of stakeholder which includes professional peers, institutional actors (both public and private), non-expert groups, and the public" (2018, p.2).

In this light, it is fundamental for heritage science to acquire stronger awareness (internal and external) on its role and mission in the socio-economic domain, besides the cultural and scientific ones.

It is a question of building a compact identity of heritage science, moving beyond fragmentation in order to establish constructive and efficient communication channels with policy-makers, to develop audience-focused strategies to attract the targeted policy-makers' attention and therefore more effectively influence the agenda setting and transnational political-institutional cooperation⁵⁴.

Attention from literature is paid increasingly also to the role that both heritage science, and conservation and restoration activities have in international diplomatic relations and in cultural diplomacy strategies⁵⁵.

The reputation obtained by some countries and scientific communities in heritage science has in fact visible impacts, reverberating on the soft power of the respective countries⁵⁶.

More specifically, E-RIHS - under certain conditions that will be discussed in the following pages - can therefore have an impact in terms of:

1. Development of **actions to support the definition of cultural policy making priorities at local, national and supranational level** (internal regulation perspective and identification of intervention priorities in the heritage sector).
2. Development of **cultural diplomacy actions**, which can also be combined with cooperation actions for cultural development (external perspective of enhancement of cultural diplomatic actions, reinforcement of international collaboration networks cultural cooperation actions).

7.1.1 Development of actions to support cultural policy making at, national and supranational level

Particularly interesting is the role that E-RIHS may have in supporting the definition of policies for heritage and heritage science, and, on a broader level, of policies aimed at improving what can be called the "heritage chain" (Zan, 2017). By "heritage chain" we mean the sequence of activities related to heritage, from archaeological-artistic discovery, to conservation, research, organization of exhibitions, opening of new museums and public access.

Restoration processes and research activities related to heritage science are in fact part of a larger and more complex system of which they represent only a small, though important part.

Moreover, these activities, in time and ways, are subordinated and conditioned to the realization of other phases of the chain: this is the case of research and restoration activities

⁵³ Many contributions have underlined the need for heritage science - understood in a broad sense - to be at the service of a wider action of strategic valorisation and policy making in the artistic and cultural domain (Brokerhof, 2015; Bell, 2015; Katrakazis, 2018 et al.).

⁵⁴ Lee, 2016.

⁵⁵ Winter, 2014a; Winter, 2014b et al.

⁵⁶ Luke, & Kersel, 2013; Akagawa, 2014; Winter, 2015 et al.

subordinated to the realization of exhibitions or to the opening of new exhibition spaces. In turn, exhibition activities are often the starting point for wider research, restoration and cultural innovation projects.

Along the chain, E-RIHS can produce and provide relevant information and scientific data for each step of the process.

The aspects on which E-RIHS can become a privileged observatory are much diversified and do not only strictly concern issues related to heritage science as a closed discipline. The extensive activities planned by E-RIHS make it possible to identify at least 5 main areas on which E-RIHS can produce relevant information and data to lobby policy-makers for constructive policies:

1. known or newly recognized heritage values
2. potential and existing risks for heritage
3. state of conservation
4. new developments in related science fields
5. problems in heritage management.

Policy-makers can prioritize actions – for example the redefinition of carrying capacity measures, or of environmental policies to contain pollutants, or the allocation of technological investments etc. - based on evidence supported by scientific data to address benefits and problems.

To realize these impacts, full awareness is required - within the heritage science field and E-RIHS - on the processes and people (at the national level) involved in policy-making. Moreover, the capacity to focus also on research topics needed to provide specific evidence for setting out strategic statements to policy-makers is fundamental⁵⁷. Finally, a specific area of impact is related to training and to the identification of the need of the training sector in terms of competencies and production of updated teaching materials.

This latter area of impact of E-RIHS is already visible from the results - in terms of books and manuals - of some projects developed within EU-ARTECH, CHARISMA, IPERION CH projects such as “Chemistry for restoration. Painting and restoration materials” (CHARISMA) which produced a specific book addressing all general and applied issues of chemistry also useful in addressing education and training needs; another examples is represented by the project “Raphael’s Painting Technique: Working Practices before Rome’s” (Eu-ARTECH) that gave as an output a book with the same title collecting together data dispersed among European and international cultural institutions on Raphael’s working practices.

The translation and subsequent knowledge dissemination are a precondition for the correct transmission of results from the heritage science community to policy makers. This translation can take place both through documents or with the mediation of advisors that, as stated by Lee (2016) – should “examine heritage issues from the standpoint of social science to evaluate heritage from a new perspective, as a resource to generate economic benefits and social solutions which can be integrated into contemporary political priorities. The benefit of heritage then should be outlined in statements drafted for different audiences including different types of policy-makers”⁵⁸. The possible transmission system from E-RIHS to the decision makers could therefore follow the scheme illustrated in Figure 17.

⁵⁷ Lee, 2016.

⁵⁸ Sujeong Lee (2015) Working with policy-makers for integrating heritage science research into political priorities, *Studies in Conservation*, vol. 60, p.55,

Figure 17. Connection paths between heritage science and decision makers

Source: author on Azevedo-Santos et al., 2017.

7.1.2 Development of cultural diplomacy actions

A second area of impact -closely related to the first one- is the development of cultural diplomacy actions, which can also be combined with cooperation actions for cultural development. Global institutions are increasingly advocating culture as an essential resource within the new paradigms of international relations and soft power Cultural diplomacy, i.e. "the skill to persuade through culture, values and ideas rather than through military means" (Nye, 2002, pp. 8-9), is therefore gaining increasingly serious recognition by the most prominent nations⁵⁹.

Given the structure of the E-RIHS partnership and its uniqueness, E-RIHS can play an important role for cultural diplomacy actions, both between partner countries and, more significantly, between Europe and other countries.

The role of culture in development processes has long been on the agenda of the international community. Already since the eighties, the Mexico City World Conference on "cultural policy" – Mundiacult (1982)⁶⁰ - affirmed that 'culture constitutes a fundamental dimension of the development process and helps to strengthen the independence, sovereignty and identity of a nation'.

Since then, interest has been growing in the role of culture for local development and in strengthening and consolidating relations - including economic ones - between countries.

The development of cooperation actions in the field of cultural heritage protection, maintenance, restoration and valorisation that has characterized the policies of many countries since the 2000s, has been strongly inspired by the deliberations of the various international forums on the role of culture for sustainable development and has its roots in the decisions of

⁵⁹ Mazzei, 2012; Cull, 2009

⁶⁰ <https://ich.unesco.org/en/1982-2000-00309>.

the Culture Counts Conference⁶¹, jointly organized by the Italian Government, UNESCO and the World Bank and held in Florence on 4-7 October 1999. Moreover today, culture is also placed at the heart of the Millennium Development Goals as its role in poverty reduction strategies and in development of a human-centered, inclusive and equitable development is universally recognized.

As well described by Carbone (2017), “in this time of global changes in terms of economic paradigms, geopolitical stability and international security, it exists the urgency of considering “culture as the fourth pillar of sustainability” (Carbone, 2011, p. 113)”.

Alongside the more traditional cooperation actions, today culture is also the object of a wider interest in terms of international relations.

In this context, E-RIHS could act as a European cultural diplomacy agent at an international level, in particular through its Hub and the national coordination units.

7.1.3 Possible Effects of E-RIHS for Agenda Setting in Cultural Policies and Cultural Diplomacy

The fact that E-RIHS can actually generate some of the outputs described above is also the conviction of the interviewed members of the coordination units with regard to the IPERION CH project (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Added value/impact of having joined IPERION CH (or joining E-RIHS ERIC) (level of agreement)

To better identify potential E-RIHS-related wider outcomes on cultural policies development and cultural diplomacy, a combined analysis of academic literature from different disciplines and case studies has been used.

In particular, the first question we tried to answer is: what effects are possible with the development of E-RIHS and its services? Which of these effects can realistically be expected?

The results are illustrated in Table 8: the first column shows the two areas of analysis "agenda setting for cultural policy" and "cultural diplomacy, cultural cooperation and soft power"; the

⁶¹ <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000122395>

second column lists a variety of possible E-RIHS-related outcomes generated by the activities carried out through ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, MOBLAB, DIGILAB, and E-RIHS Academy.

Table 8. E-RIHS areas of impact and potential for Cultural Policies and Cultural Diplomacy

E-RIHS AREAS OF WIDER IMPACT	POTENTIAL E-RIHS ENABLING ACTIVITIES
SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY BUILDING AND VISIBILITY	Promotion of an international heritage science identity by fostering information’s codification processes and data sharing, and promoting European excellence in heritage science.
CULTURAL POLICY AGENDA SETTING AND REGULATORY ACTION	<p>Provide tangible and intangible sources of information to ease the policy decision-making processes and to facilitate dialogue between policy makers and cultural institutions.</p> <p>Provide information, scientific advisory, consultancy, networking, monitoring and analysis for the heritage sector national and international policies (being point of reference also for international organizations such as UNESCO, ICOM etc.)</p>
CONTRIBUTION TO SOFT POWER AND CULTURAL DIPLOMACY ACTIONS	<p>Enabling programs and events involving policy makers and professionals from different countries, promoting cultural cooperation and support as part of domestic or foreign policy.</p> <p>Provide opportunity for smaller countries to be included into large cultural cooperation programs and to promote their identity and their heritage science excellences.</p> <p>Providing technical assistance and international coordination for international / global projects related to major restoration, major exhibitions for international anniversaries/celebrations or cultural events.</p> <p>Provision of material and technical support (instruments and knowledge) in case of natural disasters (floods, earthquakes, wars etc.), supporting institutions for a more rapid and efficient development of a rescue plan.</p>

For each identified area of wider impact, some examples have been identified (see Annex) also taken from scientific areas other than heritage science. The proposed schematization responds to a purely explanatory function and naturally many other relevant cases could be mentioned. The enablers of these impacts are analysed in the next paragraph.

7.1.4 How to reach the goal?

Those just described are just some of the possible effects of E-RIHS on Cultural Policies and Cultural Diplomacy. Case analysis helps us to identify the enabling factors and the impact pathways.

Figure 19 describes the possible paths, actions and their targets that will allow E-RIHS to actually have an impact in these areas.

It is clear that a fundamental condition for the realization of these wider impacts will be the ability of E-RIHS to translate and disseminate the results of the supported research projects to the various targets and downstream users, and to create codification standards based on the knowledge generated. Moreover, it must be taken into account that there are also a number of exogenous enabling conditions that cannot be directly controlled by E-RIHS regarding, as an example, political relations between countries, national internal political condition etc.

The dissemination activities are obviously very different depending on the role that E-RIHS will take in terms of supporting cultural policy making at national and international level and a first

important step will be to efficient communication channels with policy-makers through conferences, workshops for the scientific community, participation of the coordination unit in international policy makers meetings, and so forth.

The same logic - with different objectives - will have to be replicated at all levels: central hub, national coordination and individual teams of financed projects.

In this sense, the internal communication action of E-RIHS will be fundamental in order to encourage the institutions and researchers involved in E-RIHS projects to apply relevant communication and dissemination methods in order to strengthen the visibility and role of E-RIHS itself.

In temporal terms, the realization of the described impacts - which must be remembered, are second level impacts – will greatly depend on this internal consensus building activity and on the ability to strengthen the sense of identity of the heritage science community.

However, it should be emphasized that E-RIHS can already count on good visibility, at least at the European level. During the informal meeting of the European Union Member State Ministers responsible for Culture and Ministers responsible for European affairs, held in Paris on 3 May 2019, only the E-RIHS was cited as example of professional and scientific networks at European level, thus making it a point of reference for Europe's cultural diplomacy actions in the field of heritage sciences. Moreover, it is also worth mentioning the presence of E-RIHS as a best practice in important reports prepared on the cultural and creative economy at the national level: this is the case, for example, of the “Io Sono Cultura 2018” report, an annual study on the Italian creative economy produced by the Italian Union of Chambers of Commerce. This is an important signal – albeit embryonic - on the possible impacts described in this study.

Figure 19. E-RIHS for cultural policies and cultural diplomacy: impact pathways and enabling factors

Source: Authors

7.2 Cultural access and tourism

The world of heritage science and its role for the understanding, interpretation, conservation, authentication, and management of cultural heritage is intertwined with that of cultural valorisation aimed at the promotion of cultural access and cultural tourism. This connection which is widely testified on an empirical and academic level, is expressed in different ways that are described in Figure 20 and its reinforcement – in the E-RIHS framework - should be highly desirable in consideration of the following macro-factors:

1. The promotion of access to culture is considered strategic by Europe in order to promote social inclusion, active citizenship and individual growth but also innovation and smart growth. Commissioner Moedas, in charge of research, Sciences and Innovation, stated in 2018 that "Cultural heritage is a limitless source of innovation where traditions meet with cutting-edge technologies. Our ambition is to make Europe the world leader in heritage-based innovation with support from Horizon 2020, the EU's research and innovation funding programme."⁶²

The new "Work Plan for Culture 2019-2022"⁶³ confirms these concepts, also affirming the importance of technology and digitalisation to create new and innovative possibilities for art and culture in terms of access, expression, preservation, dissemination and consumption. The activities covered by E-RIHS offer many important tools and knowledge for the realization of these objectives which are both socio-cultural and economic

2. Cultural heritage is one of the main travel motivations for tourists worldwide: today tourism represents 10% of World's GDP (direct, indirect, induced) with 118 million people directly employed in the sector and 1,323 million International Tourist Arrivals in the world. Europe is the world's largest tourism region welcoming over 600 million international tourists every year. Tourism is therefore one of the most interesting sectors of all, also thanks to its pervasive and transversal effects on the local economies and its ability to generate employment. Nonetheless, today's tourists, with their new categories and clusters of millennials or of grey-haired globetrotters, have quite different rhythms, curiosities and interests than in the past. Moreover, many new tourist markets have opened up in recent years. As a consequence, many operators are taking action to improve their hospitality culture and to innovate their services, which means also providing cultural tourists with the right interpretative tools for enjoying a fully accessible experience, particularly in destinations/sites with a strong cultural vocation. Cultural attractors must therefore find new innovative ways and new contents to better communicate themselves to large and culturally and demographically diversified publics⁶⁴. Again, the activities that will be implemented through E-RIHS can make an important contribution in terms of induced effects of innovation of products and services for cultural heritage fruition. This is the case, for example, of in-depth analysis and new narratives on works of art, new tools that are deriving / used for restoration activities (e.g. 3D scanning and printing, photographic surveys and others) etc.

⁶² https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_18_2061.

⁶³ See "Draft Council conclusions on the Work Plan for Culture 2019-2022" (<http://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-13948-2018-INIT/en/pdf#http://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-13948-2018-INIT/en/pdf>)

⁶⁴ Friel, M., Peres A. (2018), *Futourism. New maps for the travel industry*, Milano, Bocconi University Press.

Figure 20. Heritage Science for Cultural Access and Tourism

Source: Authors

Despite the relevance that these trends could have for the application of some of the results produced by E-RIHS-funded projects on downstream users, the survey conducted on the national coordinators highlight the common understanding that this may be not one of the key direct impact of E-RIHS since the link between the activities of E-RIHS research and the world of tourism and cultural participation appears rather loose.

Figure 21. National coordinators level of agreement on the fact that E-RIHS will increase cultural tourism and audience engagement in museums by promoting the development of new products and services

Source: Survey to providers

Therefore, despite the fact that the majority of the interviewed say they agree on the fact that E-RIHS can possibly stimulate cultural tourism, a large part does not see a clear direction to reach this goal. This confirming the fact that cultural tourism is not a direct objective of E-RIHS but a possible further fallout.

The next section intends to identify the possible effects of E-RIHS on cultural access and tourism development.

7.2.1 Possible effects of E-RIHS on access to culture and cultural tourism

A first step of analysis concerned the identification of E-RIHS-related potential outcomes on cultural access and on the promotion of cultural tourism in the various countries of the network. This, suggesting that E-RIHS, pursuing the objective of favouring an interdisciplinary approach and the coordination of different operators, can thus also favour the translation and transmission of new knowledge towards the more downstream operators: users rather than knowledge producers.

These outcomes have been identified through a combined analysis of academic literature from different disciplines: heritage science, museums studies, and cultural and tourism management. The analysis of the academic literature was then supplemented by an analysis of specialized press articles and by interviews with sector operators.

In particular, the first question we tried to answer is: what effects are possible with the development of E-RIHS and its services? Which of these effects can realistically be expected? And what are the enabling conditions/actions that must be carried out in E-RIHS in order for these impacts to be realized?

The results are illustrated in Table 9: the first column shows the two areas of analysis "cultural access" and "new services for cultural fruition and cultural tourism"; the second column lists a variety of possible E-RIHS-related outputs generated for cultural access and tourism promotion by ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, MOBLAB, DIGILAB, E-RIHS Academy; finally, the third column gives some specific examples looking at already existing comparable products and services.

Table 9. E-RIHS areas of wider impact and potential products/services for cultural access and tourism

E-RIHS areas of Wider impact	Potential E-RIHS-related products and services implemented by downstream operators	Examples of products and services produced by downstream operators
CULTURAL ACCESS The contents generated by E-RIHS for purpose of research, conservation, restoration and archiving are used for scientific dissemination, for training activities of non-specialist public, or for providing access to cultural heritage to persons with disabilities.	Products and services for education	3D printed miniatures for art education in schools
	Products and services to promote wide cultural access for general public	Digital archives and collections; Film and art documentaries on restoration activities etc.
	Products and services to make inaccessible or endangered heritage, accessible	Digital tools such as augmented and virtual reality, diffusion of images and filming, at very high resolution etc.
NEW SERVICES FOR CULTURAL FRUITION AND CULTURAL TOURISM The contents generated by E-RIHS for research, conservation, restoration and archiving give life to new exhibitions, new museums, new services for cultural fruition enhancing also the experience of cultural tourist.	Exhibitions	Exhibitions on restored works of arts, "live" restoration, and exhibitions on reunification of works of art.
	Museums	New museums specifically designed to host restored/rediscovered works of art.
	Services	Tools for cultural accessibility of people with disabilities such as 3D printed interactive audio guides.

To identify these possible products and services developed by E-RIHS downstream users, a number of case studies and examples were analysed at the European and international level, which are reported in Annex III.

The cases presented are made up of products, new devices and services developed by museums and other cultural institutions, cultural enterprises, and creative and technological start-ups in connection with restoration activities, scientific insights on works of art or findings from archival research activities. The proposed schematization responds to an explanatory function, as it is clear that the two areas of impact intersect: products and services developed to improve access to culture for the general public can then have an impact also on heritage tourism development. This because, by introducing innovative tools and services to experience culture, on the one hand the institutions and sites that are using these innovations can become more attractive for different categories of public, including tourists, on the other because a more developed culture of innovation and access is generally associated with audience engagement policies that are also functional for the enlargement also of a public made by tourists.⁶⁵ Moreover, the identified "Products and Services" should not be understood as a direct result of the activities of E-RIHS but as collateral areas of application/replicability/scalability of projects developed within E-RIHS.

7.2.2 How to reach the goal?

Following the identification of the possible areas of impact, it is also important to try to identify trace the possible pathways enabling the desired impacts to occur.

A first point concerns the type of projects accepted by E-RIHS and the methods of access to E-RIHS services but also on the typology of educational and outreach activities that will be implemented.

With regard to the first point, in fact, it will be possible not only to give preferential access to projects that will have a greater impact in these areas but also to stimulate an ex-ante reflection by the requesting projects in order to clarify the expected impacts on cultural access, and on the production of new products and services for the general public. In particular, the projects, already in the presentation phase, should specify objectives and related actions and result indicators with reference to cultural access.

By way of example, E-RIHS applicants should consider to address the following questions when presenting their applications:

1. Can the outputs of the restoration, research, analysis activities find direct and immediate use for cultural dissemination activities? If so, how? Under what conditions, through which additional activities (dissemination workshops, re-use of images and data, training, expertise acquisition) and what would be the costs in terms of money and time?
2. The projects that access physical facilities (FIXLAB, MOLAB, ARCHLAB) and digital facilities (DIGILAB), do also include actors that can favour these impacts? If not, are there any additional actors that can be included, and under what conditions?

Figure 22 describes the possible impact pathways and enabling conditions that will allow E-RIHS to actually have an impact on the conception and implementation of new cultural and tourist products and services by downstream actors.

⁶⁵ Friel, M., & Peres, A. (2019). *Futourism: A New Map for Travel Tomorrow*. EGEA Spa-Bocconi University Press.

Figure 22. E-RIHS ERIC for cultural access and tourism: impact pathways and enabling factors

8. Conclusions and recommendations

The implementation of E-RIHS ERIC can positively contribute to multiple objectives the heritage science community is pursuing such as building a common identity and moving beyond fragmentation, advancing and scaling-up heritage science research, and fostering interinstitutional research and policy collaboration in this field. The analysis presented in this report describes the pathways leading to these goals and measures, as far as possible, the expected impacts on the community by the establishment of the ERIC.

Direct impacts, that is to say those affecting the scientific community (scientific and human capital impact) as well as the wider public (dissemination and outreach) directly using E-RIHS services, are worth about EUR 71 million (at 2017) prices in the baseline scenario. When compared to the costs needed to set-up and operate the infrastructure, the B/C ratio is above 1, pointing to a net positive contribution to the community of users. The most prominent direct economic benefits are efficiency gains related to the coordinated access to platforms and scientific information, and the advance of knowledge by means of publications, which in turn result in science production. Overall, the science production accounts for 75% of the total value of direct impacts. Other direct impacts include the development of human capital and benefits from dissemination and outreach activities via social media.

Indirect and wider impacts may also be generated as a consequence of the activities of E-RIHS ERIC. This report identifies two main impact pathways. By one side, E-RIHS is likely to contribute to science diplomacy by incentivising scientific collaborations among nations and institutions and building constructive international partnerships, and therefore impact on the heritage science policy at European, if not at global level. On the other side, it has the potential to generate impacts in terms of access to culture by the public and increasing cultural tourism. Although potentially very interesting, the impacts described above should be considered as second level impacts. Their ability to be realized in fact does not depend only on the E-RIHS ability - at its different levels - to disseminate the results of its research activities and to make the new technologies developed reusable and scalable. In this specific case, a central role for the final development of new products and services depends on a series of operators and private companies active on the territories of reference.

The ability of E-RIHS to raise the awareness of the heritage science community on the characteristics of downstream users, and to foster application of research results, must in fact be combined with business development in the private sector and with a strong mediating/facilitating role by museums and cultural institutions.

Both direct and indirect impacts should not be taken for granted, in the sense that the mere implementation of operations envisaged by E-RIHS ERIC does not lead to the materialisation of benefits by default. As shown by the logical model, the causal chains linking inputs to impacts are diverse, non-linear, and different enabling conditions (internal and external to E-RIHS) need to be met and activated. E-RIHS ERIC management is called to create the right circumstances for the societal impact to materialise.

Based on this analysis and thinking the socioeconomic impact as process rather than as product of E-RIHS' activities, the following actions can keep the initiative on the right pathways for impacts:

- **A sustainable level of demand aiming at reaching the number of TNA users of physical platforms foreseen in the baseline scenario should be ensured.** The CBA indicates that there is a break-even point at 650 TNA users. Under this level of demand, costs to provide a coordinated and unique access exceed their benefits and the ENPV turns to be negative. Increasing the share of machine- and personnel-time for E-RIHS users, expanding the network of affiliated facilities, and ensuring a good level of coordination among spatially distributed providers can increase the appeal of E-RIHS services. In parallel, information campaigns aiming at reducing the information gap experienced by potential users as regards the type of services and facilities offered, mode of access, and the necessary skills to use instrumentation are likely to increase the users' awareness about the value of services provided. However, a critical aspect is the capacity to ensure the coverage of financial costs to access E-RIHS (e.g. cost of travel and subsistence to access services, cost of transportation and insurance for mobile machine).
- **Efforts should be concentrated to create high added-value services for users.** The existence of E-RIHS is legitimised as long as it makes easier and cheaper the access to existing facilities, and therefore offering services that add value as compared to the existing access situation. The removal of administrative, managerial, and cultural barriers depends on to what extent E-RIHS will be able to coordinate users when accessing (e.g. providing assistance in developing project proposals, help desk activities, conveying complete and clear information via its web portal), to offer integrating services (e.g. access to multiple platforms and complementary research equipment), and actually providing FAIR data via DIGILAB. It is also advised to continue with training courses (e.g. training camps, summer schools), which represent valuable services from the attendees' viewpoint.
- **Contributing to the preparation of a policy agenda for heritage science by adopting a prioritisation mechanism for the identification of the community's needs** should be considered among the internal enabling conditions to make E-RIHS a key actor for heritage science policy. Science diplomacy, support to policy design with programming and regulatory tools, and advocacy can be triggered by E-RIHS by facilitating a close dialogue among its partners, organising international conferences, increasing its international visibility, and participating at heritage science events. These activities help build an identity and make E-RIHS' voice heard when interfacing with policy-makers and key institutions in setting the policy agenda at the international level.
- **The engagement of actors such as SMEs (or their representativeness) and operators in the cultural tourism sector** is an additional enabling condition to trigger downstream impacts. While the main mission of E-RIHS is to promote excellence in research, and therefore downstream impacts are beyond its main scope, **co-creation is likely to create the bridge linking E-RIHS research activities to the economy by means of knowledge transfer to firms and cultural and tourism operators.** Collaboration practises between researchers and firms during a research project or further dissemination and communication activities can produce a mutually valuable outcome: researchers make their results usable beyond the scientific community; firms may increase their

innovation capabilities and develop new products and services to be used in the cultural tourism sector.

- **E-RIHS ERIC management should keep track of the identified Key Performance Indicators for future monitoring and evaluation activities, which should be driven by the logic model developed ad-hoc for E-RIHS.** The idea of the societal impact as a process requires to periodically monitor whether deviations from the ex-ante forecasts, targets or modified enabling conditions occur and in that case assess to what extent they can jeopardise the impact of E-RIHS on the reference group of users. Updates of the current analysis or new evaluation exercises can be considered in the future as strategic tool to ensure that E-RIHS ERIC is on the right pathway and (new) objectives are within reach.

List of interviews

Name	Affiliation	Date
Gabriele Gori	<i>Fondazione Cassa di Risparmio di Firenze</i> (Director General)	18/10/2018
Costanza Milani	<i>CNR-ISTM (National Research Council - Institute of Molecular Science and Technologies)</i> (Senior researcher and Scientific coordinator of access service to MOLAB),	31/10/2018 and December 2018
Marco Ciatti	<i>Opificio delle Pietre Dure</i> (Superintendent)	7/11/2018
Cecilia Frosinini	<i>Opificio delle Pietre Dure</i> (Director at Fortezza da Basso)	8/11/2018
Monica Galeotti	<i>Opificio delle Pietre Dure</i> (Chemist and Director)	8/11/2018
Roberto Ferrari	Department of Culture and Research of Tuscany Region (Director)	8/11/2018
Luca De Santis	<i>Net7</i> (Chief Technology Officer)	13/11/2018
Irina Crina Anca Sandu	<i>Conservation Department of the Munch Museum of Oslo</i> (Director)	05/12/18
Christina Scibè	<i>University of Seville</i> (PhD in Conservation Science)	12/12/18
Hilde De Clercq	KIK- IRPA (Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage) (Algemeen Director and Scientific coordinator of access service to ARCHLAB)	12/02/19
Michel Menu	<i>C2MRF</i> (Director and Scientific coordinator of access service to FIXLAB)	12/02/19
Claudia Invernizzi	<i>University of Pavia and Museo del Violino di Cremona</i> (Conservation Scientist)	18/02/19
Romain Thomas	<i>Université Paris Nanterre</i> (Professor of History of the Modern Art and Vice-director of the History of Arts and Archeology Department)	5/03/19

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